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MYRTUS

Multi-layer 360° dYnamic orchestration and interopeRable design environmenT for compute-continUum Systems

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1 Executive Summary

This deliverable reports the results of WP1 during the first 8 months of the project. As shown in Table 1-1, this deliverable reports on the activities of both “T1.1 - Assessment scenarios: preliminary specifications” and “T1.2 - MYRTUS TransContinuum approach: preliminary specifications” and it is meant to provide a draft “UC requirements/needs, technical specifications, and KPIs definition to guide project Phase 1 development”

Indeed, as a result of T1.1 activities, this document provides the preliminary description of the MYRTUS assessment scenarios with their expected functionalities, offered services, and needs. Additionally, as a result of T1.2 activities, this document reports on MYRTUS technical specifications. It is going to provide the preliminary intended mapping of the MYRTUS computing continuum approach considering the reference architecture promoted by the European Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum Initiative. Moreover, the expected requirements and Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) are defined per technical pillar of the project.

Table 1-1: D1.1 description from the Grant Agreement

D1.1 - UC Needs, requirements and KPIs v1 - M8

UC requirements/needs, technical specifications, KPIs definition to guide project Phase 1 development.

Task Involved:

T1.1(M1-M6) - Assessment scenarios: preliminary specifications [TNO(L), ALL]

T1.2(M1-M8) - MYRTUS TransContinuum approach: preliminary specifications [ABI (L), ALL]

2 Introduction

WP1 is composed of two main tasks, which initial results are reported in this document.

T1.1, started at M1 and completed at M6, under the guidance of TNO, involved both Use Case (UC) providers and technology providers. The goal was to provide a preliminary definition of the project assessment scenarios, the *Healthcare* and *Smart Mobility* one. The result of this activity is reported in Section 3 below. Moreover, a preliminary UC to Technology Mapping activity has been carried out and reported in Section 4.4 below. This activity has been carried out in between T1.1 and T1.2.

T1.2 started at M1 and completed at M8. The scientific coordinator and WP3, WP5 and WP7 leaders worked in close cooperation to refine the project's big picture (see Section 4 below) while in parallel, ABI (task leader) defined and coordinated the process behind the technical requirements gathering (see Section 5 below).

Please note that this document is the first of its kind. Following the two-phase iterative approach that characterizes MYRTUS project work plan, this deliverable will be updated at M22 by “D2.1 UC - Needs, requirements and KPIs v2” considering the feedback from partial technology assessment (WP9 outcome), M18 review, and synergy-related activities (with the other computing continuum initiatives/projects and the cluster 3 projects).

2.1 Structure of the Document

The rest of the deliverable is structured as follows.

- Section 3 – Reports T1.1 activities, presenting MYRTUS assessment scenarios from the Use Case providers perspective.
- Section 4 – Reports primarily T1.2 activities, presenting the update of MYRTUS big-picture with respect to the Grant Agreement. MYRTUS methodology and expected results mapped to Operational Objectives (OOs) and KPIs per technical pillar are presented. This section concludes with a preliminary description of the Assessment Scenarios to Results mapping, which is an activity carried out hand in hand with T1.1.
- Section 5 – Reports on the T1.2 activities specifically related to the requirements gathering and management process. Please note that in this document the emphasis is on the process itself, while the complete requirements file is provided as a confidential annex to the deliverable.
- Section 6 – Concludes with some final remarks.

3 Preliminary specification of MYRTUS assessment scenarios

To detail and refine the description of the assessment scenarios, starting from Table 7 Section 1.2.5.c of the Grant Agreement, we defined a new UC table capable of providing an overview of:

- **UC identity data:** including information on the owner, initially involved partners, and the application domain.
- **UC overview:** providing a high-level overview of the UC, both from the application point of view (Application Diagram) and from the deployment (Deployment Diagram) point of view. Moreover, in this section the offered services and the expected human role in the cyber-physical system is described.
- **UC requirements:** describing the requested functionalities and the operating modes (through user stories and connected expected system behaviour). Moreover, the foreseen evolution and learning capabilities and the baseline technical constraints are also provided.
- **UC evaluation:** including a definition of the already existent baseline and the expected functional and non-functional UC specific evaluation metrics.

The skeleton of the table used to specify the assessment scenarios along with the expected content (in the form of the instructions provided to the UC owners to provide all the above-mentioned information) is reported in Table 3-1. In the following subsections the results of the Healthcare and the Smart Mobility UCs are reported in their individual tables.

The activities that led to the tables reported in the two following subsections have been carried out mainly by UC owners and the scientific coordinator. Regular biweekly calls starting from February 2024 till end of March 2024 have been organised to homogenise descriptions to be provided to the rest of the consortium partners. Technology providers received these descriptions as a starting point for the Use Case to Technology mapping activity carried out in T1.2 and reported in Section 4.4.

Table 3-1 - Skeleton of the Use Case specification table. The text in red are the instructions provided to the UC owners to refine the descriptions already provided in the Grant Agreement.

Use Case (UC) Title	
UC identity data	
UC Owner	
Involved Partners	<i>Initial list of involved partners. Please note that it might change along project development</i>
Application Domain	
UC overview	
Application Diagram	<i>UML style UC diagram</i>
Application Diagram description	<i>UC diagram description with emphasis on the high-level application overview</i>
Deployment Diagram	<i>Application to components mapping</i>
Deployment Diagram description	<i>UC set-up description in terms of physical components where the different tasks/services will be executed</i>
Offered services	<i>List of potential services for final end-user</i>

Expected human role	<p><i>MYRTUS intends to provide technologies for CPS with a living dimension where the cyber system and humans are not simply “connected” or “interactive”. CPS with a living dimension is expected to “become capable of both cooperating with their human mates and of inducing positive, environmental-friendly, human behaviours”</i></p> <p><i>Referring to Table 7 of the Grant Agreement, please revise and extend the expected human role.</i></p>
UC Requirements	
Requested functionalities	<p><i>List and description of algorithms and computing tasks. Please refer to any state-of-the-art or open-source implementation (e.g. GitHub) if available.</i></p>
Expected Operating modes - User Stories	<p><i>Definition of the initial set of scenarios (described as user stories) to be handled prospectively throughout the MIRTO cognitive engine. Please highlight the differences among the scenarios in terms of functionality.</i></p>
Expected Operating modes - System Expected Behaviour behind the User Stories	<p><i>Definition of the expected system behaviour, in terms of resource management, behind the identified scenarios. You can leverage users' stories to explain what is expected to happen at the system level and based on which triggers.</i></p>
Evolution and Learning capabilities	<p><i>Referring to Table 7 of the Grant Agreement, please revise and extend the evolution and learning capabilities, based on the defined scenarios and user stories. Explain how they are expected to evolve and learn during execution.</i></p>
Technical Constraints	<p><i>Referring to Table 7 of the Grant Agreement, please revise and extend all the technical constraints in terms of latency, bandwidth capacity, power/energy efficiency, and processing elements.</i></p>
UC Evaluation	
Baseline	<p><i>What is there now? What is the state of the art? Please refer to the evaluation KPIs that you intend to measure in your scenario. Please also include the UC specific and impact-oriented ones. You can leverage the following classification.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Qualitative baseline ● Quantitative Baseline
Expectation and needs	<p><i>Referring to Table 7 of the Grant Agreement, please revise and extend all the needs in terms of Scalability, Adaptivity, Cooperativeness and Dependability. Given the already defined baseline, please describe your realistic expectations in terms of needs, consider the application and usage of MYRTUS technologies at the end of the project. You can leverage the following classification.</i></p> <p>Qualitative goals: Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Novel use/integration ... to achieve/guarantee ...</i> <p>Quantitative goals: Examples:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Improvement of XX%</i> ● <i>Increase of YYY%</i>

- Reduction of KK%

3.1 Healthcare Use Case - Swarm-inspired cooperative telerehabilitation

Healthcare UC	
UC identity data	
UC Owner	UNICA
Involved Partners	<p>UNICA MeDSP: The UNICA MeDSP Lab defines the exergames and the key players who are part of it, the interaction models, the body signals acquisition and their integration in the Virtual Reality (VR) scenarios, also modelling pre-defined and probability-driven autonomous swarm behaviour for the Virtual Agents (VAs). It investigates possible exergames scenarios. Finally, it deals with defining the methods and tests for validating the proposed system.</p> <p>REPLY: Infinity Reply mainly works closely with UNICA in shaping and developing the Healthcare Use Case, by designing the exergames, defining the solution architecture, producing the 3D assets, and developing the networked VR multi-users layer.</p>
Application Domain	Healthcare
UC overview	
<p>Application Diagram (Note that the high-quality version of this diagram is attached in Appendix 1)</p>	<pre> graph TD P1[Patient 1] --- UC1((P2P communication within the game)) P1 --- UC2((Rendering of VR scenario and avatars)) P1 --- UC3((Rendering of VR scenario and avatars)) P1 --- UC4((Actuation)) P1 --- UC5((Read data from physical sensors)) P1 --- UC6((Preprocess data from sensors)) P1 --- UC7((Compute behaviors of avatars and game objects)) P1 --- UC8((Adaptive behaviors and learning)) P1 --- UC9((Real-time resource monitoring and resource orchestration)) P1 --- UC10((Handover Computation task)) P1 --- UC11((Vertical Handover Edge-FOG/Cloud)) P1 --- UC12((Horizontal Handover-edge)) P2[Patient 2] --- UC1 P2 --- UC2 P2 --- UC3 P2 --- UC4 P2 --- UC5 P2 --- UC6 P2 --- UC7 P2 --- UC8 P2 --- UC9 P2 --- UC10 P2 --- UC11 P2 --- UC12 T[Therapist] --- UC1 T --- UC2 T --- UC3 T --- UC13((Collect patients' needs and set win conditions)) T --- UC14((log session data)) T --- UC15((Instantiate virtual agents)) T --- UC16((Instantiate responsive game-elements)) VA1[Virtual agent 1] --- UC1 VA1 --- UC2 VA1 --- UC3 VA1 --- UC4 VA1 --- UC5 VA1 --- UC6 VA1 --- UC7 VA1 --- UC8 VA1 --- UC9 VA1 --- UC10 VA1 --- UC11 VA1 --- UC12 VA2[Virtual agent 2] --- UC1 VA2 --- UC2 VA2 --- UC3 VA2 --- UC4 VA2 --- UC5 VA2 --- UC6 VA2 --- UC7 VA2 --- UC8 VA2 --- UC9 VA2 --- UC10 VA2 --- UC11 VA2 --- UC12 UC1 --- UC2 UC2 --- UC3 UC3 --- UC4 UC4 --- UC5 UC5 --- UC6 UC6 --- UC7 UC7 --- UC8 UC8 --- UC9 UC9 --- UC10 UC10 --- UC11 UC11 --- UC12 UC13 --- UC14 UC14 --- UC15 UC15 --- UC16 UC10 -.-> UC11 UC10 -.-> UC12 </pre>

<p>Application Diagram description</p>	<p><i>[Note that just the main actors/blocks are described below]</i></p> <p>The diagram considers both the physical/real world and the virtual environment/entities. Actors in this diagram are both physical (patients, P, and therapist, T) and virtual (virtual agents, VAs, and responsive game-element).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Patients may be more than one, Patient_{1, 2,...N}. ● The therapist may participate in the online training session along with the patients, but not necessarily, assuming a dual role: he/she can act as a patient (e.g. any Patient_x) or just see the scenes in “God” mode and selectively interact to set win conditions and instantiate VAs (therapist in the schema). The win conditions are the conditions/parameters that the patient must meet during the exercise to enable a progression toward the goal. For instance, in a dragon boat exergame, the patient should be able to correctly synchronise with the other rowers, beyond further movement-quality conditions, to push the boat efficiently along the course of a river and reach the end of a maze: thresholds on the behaviour of the boat with respect to the actual synchronisation level to achieve movement, turning, etc, are examples of win conditions. The therapist can record, and store data generated during a therapy session (“log session data” block in the schema). This block is crucial for monitoring and analysing activities performed, patient progress, and therapy effectiveness. This information will be leveraged and appropriately synchronised by the “compute behaviours of avatar and game objects” block in the schema. ● In contrast to physical users, the VA is an entity already integrated into virtual reality as a 3D model, instantiated by the game server according to the therapist's indication to support a specific patient. Indeed, the patients, because of their condition, may have mobility or interaction problems, thus exhibiting difficulties in performing the exergame. ● The Responsive game-element can be considered as another type of VA that is integrated into the virtual scene to be responsible for sensing and intervening in the evolution of the game by creating attractors, distractors, and in general environmental changes able to provide reward or penalty and to foster the development of specific behaviours in the group. <p>The users (physical agents) wear the sensors and VR headset. All the sensors and devices worn by a user communicate with a hub (which can be represented simply by the VR headset in case of a reduced set of sensors) to provide information exploited to act in the virtual reality scene, such as translating the user's movement in the real environment into the avatar movement in the virtual environment. This function is implemented by the “read data from physical sensor” block in the schema. When a large number of sensors is used, an external hardware hub could be necessary to collect and preprocess sensors' data to reduce the bandwidth for the communication with the headset and its computational burden. This function (either implemented on the hub or not) is implemented by the “preprocess data from sensor” block in the schema. Each VR headset sends the local information (position, orientation, and movements information, ...)</p>
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and receives the information coming from (a limited number of) the other agents, both virtual and real, to locally render this information and create a scene where all of them are correctly represented and animated. This function is implemented by the "[compute behaviors of avatar and game objects](#)" block in the schema; this is nothing more than the front-end of the game server, which is responsible for synchronising all the data and can be physically hosted in a low-latency cloud. Once the data have been synchronised, an action is generated (e.g., the boat will move down the river with a specific speed and direction). If the resulting action respects the conditions set by the therapist, then a global reward is assigned. In case this resulting action does not respect these rules, a penalty is assigned. This reward and penalty information is managed by the responsive game-element. For example, if the game is not evolving with an acceptable level of complexity even in terms of achieving a neurorehabilitative outcome for patients, the responsive game-element can engage the users by introducing attractors, distractors, etc. This function is implemented by the "[instantiate responsive game-elements](#)" block in the schema.

The behaviour of the VA adapts to changes in the environment and the action of other users and can influence it, see "[adaptive behaviour](#)" block in the schema. To realise this behaviour, the VA should exchange information with the front-end of the game server as the headset of every physical user would do. As such, the VA can be computed in the game server, in the user clients, or in other cloud resources.

Each user of the game (patients and therapist) can communicate directly with other participants through "[P2P communication within the game](#)" direct communication without the need for a central server.

The VR environment, as well as all users participating in the game, will be generated through a three-dimensional creation and visualisation process ("[Rendering of VR scenario and avatars](#)" block in the schema).

To ensure that any changes or information (user positions, movements and interactions) are immediately reflected in the VR environment the rendering block is closely related to the "[Send stream of information to update the VR client](#)" block.

To handle the instantiation and execution of VAs, a process closely related to the computation request, there is the "[Real-time resource monitoring and resource orchestration](#)" block in the schema, which is connected to the game server and adaptive behaviours and learning. Patients and therapists are connected to an edge, and they will always be on edge. The VAs are not bound to a specific location. Therefore, they are connected to an orchestration flow that can decide upon their vertical (cross-layer, "[vertical handover](#)" block in the schema) or horizontal (intra-layer "[horizontal handover](#)" block in the schema) dispatching, depending on the current execution conditions. Learning and the adaptive behaviour of VAs can take place everywhere (fog or edge).

<p>Deployment Diagram (Note that the high-quality version of this diagram is attached in Appendix 1)</p>	
<p>Deployment Diagram description</p>	<p>In the Deployment Diagram, each actor is shown in the layer (edge, fog, cloud) it operates on.</p> <p>The users (patient or therapist) wearing the VR headset will have their computation done locally.</p> <p>The therapists (acting as an invisible observer) will have their computation done locally on a Windows desktop device.</p> <p>Sensors will send data to a local HUB at the edge, which processes the data, and sends it back to the VR user.</p> <p>VAs run either on the edge or the fog, depending on the decision made by the MIRTO cognitive engine. When the orchestrator detects excessive computational complexity on the edge, it might shift part of the computation to the fog.</p> <p>In the cloud, on the game server side, runs the Network Synchronisation entity that receives shared data from all users and ensures that each entity has a shared view of the scene. Common entities for all users will also run in the cloud. For example, in the game "Dragon Boat," the behaviour of the boat is calculated on the server side and must be the same for all connected clients.</p> <p>There is also a provision for storing patient report data. These can either be kept locally or uploaded to the server at the end of the session.</p>
<p>Offered services</p>	<p>For the patient: home-based or hospital/clinic-based telerehabilitation by advanced immersive and haptic virtual reality environment, with the challenge of collaborative tasks, no matter the number of simultaneously connected patients, for</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Cognitive and behavioural rehabilitation ● Motor rehabilitation ● Neuromotor rehabilitation <p>For the therapist: possibility to monitor the patients' progress, interacting in the virtual environment with them, supporting or challenging them by the inclusion of VAs with specific goals.</p>
<p>Expected human role</p>	<p>Patients are the main human actors: they perform rehabilitation training in a virtual environment by interacting with other users to carry out a collaborative task, which involves both motor and cognitive loads. Patients can only control their own activity.</p> <p>Therapists are other actors in the system: they can control and change the parameters associated with specific patients to motivate them more. To support or challenge specific patients, they can instantiate VAs programmed</p>

	<p>to emulate specific behaviours (distractors, supporters, ...). Moreover, they could directly communicate with individual patients by voice or video calls, or text messages, to provide feedback, or help and encourage them in a difficult situation.</p>
<p>UC Requirements</p>	
<p>Requested functionalities</p>	<p>Real-time multiplayer games rely on prediction to maintain the illusion of real-time synchronisation across all clients. The most common prediction algorithms used are:</p> <p>Client-Side Interpolation: This method makes movements smoother by guessing between known states. For example, if there's a delay in receiving an object's next position, the game engine can guess its movement, updating the position until new data arrives. The server periodically sends state updates to the client. Instead of immediately updating the positions of objects to the new values received, the client keeps a small "cache" of these states. The client then interpolates between these states, calculating intermediate positions based on the received data. For example, if the server sends updates every 100ms, the client can use this data to calculate intermediate positions every frame (e.g., 16ms for a game running at 60fps). Some examples of Client-Side interpolation algorithm are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Linear Interpolation (LERP): It calculates the intermediate position between two points (states) in a straight line. Formula: $P(t) = (1-t) * P1 + t * P2$ where $P(t)$ is the interpolated position, $P1$ and $P2$ are the known positions, and t is the interpolation factor ($0 \leq t \leq 1$). ● Cubic Interpolation: This method uses a cubic function to calculate the intermediate position, providing smoother transitions than linear interpolation, especially during changes in direction. Formula: the formula can vary but involves a cubic polynomial. an example is: $P(t) = a * t^3 + b * t^2 + c * t + d$ where a, b, c and d are coefficients determined by the known points and their derivatives. ensuring a very smooth and natural transition. <p>Client-Side Prediction and Correction of Prediction: This allows the game to predict the result of actions without waiting for server confirmation. It's useful for actions like movement but requires a way to correct differences between the game's predictions and the server's state. Some examples are:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Dead Reckoning: It predicts the future position of an object based on its last known position, velocity, and direction. This method assumes that the object will continue moving in the same manner until new data is received from the server. Formula: $P_{predicted} = P_{last} + v * \Delta t$ where $P_{predicted}$ is the predicted position, P_{last} is the last known position, v is the velocity and Δt is the time elapsed since the last known position. ● Input Prediction: It involves the client predicting the game state by simulating the effects of user inputs before receiving confirmation from the server. Formula: $S_{predicted} = S_{current} + f(I)$ where $S_{predicted}$ is the predicted state, $S_{current}$ is the current state and $f(I)$ is the function that applies input I. ● Reconciliation: It corrects the client's game state based on updates received from the server while maintaining a smooth gameplay experience. Step(s): i) Detects the discrepancy between the predicted

	<p>state and the server's state. ii) Applies a correction over several frames to avoid a jarring transition.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Time Warp: It is a method that involves rewinding the game state to a previous point in time to handle late-arriving inputs. Step(s): i) Saves a history of game states. ii) When a delayed input is received, rewinds to the appropriate state. iii) Applies the input and re-simulates all actions up to the current state. <p>Lag Compensation: Servers can use techniques to account for a player's latency. This ensures that actions are evaluated as if they occurred immediately, despite the delay in data reception.</p>
<p>Expected Operating modes - User Stories</p>	<p>Flavio Rossi, a post-stroke patient followed by Dr. Andrea Giuliani, needs a neurorehabilitation session.</p> <p>The therapist suggested a one-hour training session three times a week; therefore, Flavio starts the first session this evening from the living room of his home.</p> <p>First, he wears the head-mounted display of the VR headset, and some wearable sensors controlling his muscle activity, switching on a sensor hub on his desk. He stands in an upright position grasping the VR controllers. In the virtual environment, his avatar, <i>Big</i>, is ready to start! In the virtual scenario, Flavio can see 3 other avatars, which represent other players available to complete the task with him. He is not able to distinguish whether the other players are real patients like him or VAs acting as patients.</p> <p>The therapist suggested playing the Dragon Boat game, which involves exploring a maze river by paddling a dragon boat. So, Flavio selects this training, and presses "start". Initially, Flavio is requested to perform a reaching movement in front of him, to paddle with his avatar: for him, this is very difficult, due to his clinical condition that impaired his proper mobility in his upper limbs. At some point in the session, Flavio perceives from the scene that he is paddling against the will of the other rowers. So, he tries to change the direction of the arm movement and go in the opposite direction from the previous action. Nonetheless, he continues to find the movement complicated and is getting tired quickly. So, he slows down a bit.</p> <p>At a certain point, a message appears in front of Flavio, suggesting that he leave the session to move to a simpler one and better understand the movements he needs to make. As he accepts, he is loaded into a safe room simpler from the previous one. Flavio tries to synchronise with the rest of the avatars and realises that the motor task is easier for him on this boat. He starts to pay attention to the extent and quality of the movement too, discovering that larger movements are more effective while co-contractions of antagonistic muscles reduce effectiveness. Quality of movement is displayed as feedback, enabling Flavio to perceive his contribution to the boat movement, compared to the others, and to improve movement control. If he reaches the threshold, a message appears saying "you have completed the training session", and he can choose to return to the homepage to start another game.</p>

	<p>In the next session, Flavio perceives that in this boat the pace is faster. The boat is moving faster now and proceeding in the right direction. At some point, Flavio realises that further ahead there is a deviation to the left of the maze, but the boat is not turning yet. Suddenly, a vortex attracts the boat and slows down its proper progress along the course of the river. Flavio then hears a voice, "Flavio! Good job so far, try to increase the speed of movement. Try to synchronise with the other rowers to get the boat to the end of the maze". Then Flavio stops the arm movement to raise the paddle on the left side of the boat and allows the other rowers to paddle only on the right side. Flavio then perceives that the boat is beginning to move in the right direction and the obstacle has been correctly avoided.</p> <p>Finally, Flavio sees that the end of the maze is approaching. When the game is over, Flavio sees "successfully completed training session" on the screen.</p> <p>The therapist would like to assist in Flavio's training session, so he decides to connect remotely.</p> <p>The therapist then sees the virtual scene evolving on his computer monitor and Flavio's avatar highlighted by a label with his name. The therapist had suggested to Flavio to play Dragon Boat in multiplayer mode. For each patient, the therapist fills out game conditions to be observed as minimum speed below which the boat cannot go, maximum deviation from the ideal path, etc. And so, knowing Flavio's clinical history, he had done the same for Flavio, figuring out an individualised rehabilitation program for him. But at one point the therapist notices that Flavio has difficulty keeping up with the pace of the boat driven by a set of 4 other patients further along in rehabilitation than him. So, the therapist decides that Flavio needs a guided session to get better ready before a new session. Later, the therapist decides that Flavio, having become familiar with the game, can return to the level he originally assigned him. Further later, as a game increases in the level of complexity of the task by adding elements to avoid, to increase the pacing or get a rest. To motivate the patient to complete the task despite the added difficulty, the therapist sends a vocal message to Flavio suggesting to increase the speed of arm movement and to cooperate and synchronise with the other rowing avatars to get around the obstacle.</p>
<p>Expected Operating modes - System Expected Behaviour behind the User Stories</p>	<p>The proposed system involves instantiating VAs based on the therapist's request or based on rules the therapist established. MIRTO cognitive engine will then have to make decisions about if and how to move the loads (the VAs). Since these are purely software entities, they could potentially run anywhere within the MYRTUS layered computing continuum infrastructure. Here follows different possible scenarios, considering higher complexity and computational demands.</p> <p>At the beginning Flavio is the only patient, P1, being initially unable to perform the task with other patients and needs to familiarise himself with the neurorehabilitation task on his own. After training with a single VA in a 2-seat boat, the system decides to pair him with 7 VAs, in the role of facilitators (normal boats have 8 seats). These VAs will be well-synchronised among them, and properly moving, well responsive to the environmental changes so that P1 can try to "follow" their behaviour. Normally, VAs could run on the sensor hub at the edge. However, such a high number of VAs might be too much for a single processing core. Therefore, MIRTO could</p>

	<p>operate vertical or horizontal orchestration to run them in the fog or in other edge devices.</p> <p>As Flavio, still P1, gets more experienced and progresses, he starts exercising with other real patients. Let's consider the case that P1 is exercising, and 4 other patients are rehabilitating at the same moment. According to the boat size, if more than 3 VAs are needed for the patients, they will be allocated to different boats in different room games. If the workload for any given edge machine is not acceptable, MIRTO could operate horizontal orchestration to better distribute the workload according to the available resources. Clearly, vertical orchestration is still an option also in this second scenario.</p> <p>Let's assume a third case, due to a level switch of a patient, demonstrating more capabilities in managing the exercise, the game server reduces the number of VAs for both P1 and P2 to 2. Then, P1 and P2 can be transferred on the same boat with 4 VAs. Two further VAs will be added to fill the boat: also in this case, a workload reallocation between the edge and fog resources can be implemented.</p> <p>Now, consider a sudden internet shutdown, which is why P2 exits the game. P2 must be excluded from the exercise, but the other patients must continue the exercise. In this case, it is necessary to instantiate 3 VAs on the fog, one replacing P2 and the others replacing his/her VAs. Similarly, if P2 exits the exercise, other VAs could be needed to enable exercising for the other patients.</p>
<p>Evolution and Learning capabilities</p>	<p>All agents, real and virtual, can learn to move in the virtual environment and participate in the collaborative task. The behaviour of VAs acting as patients is constrained by a predetermined set of local rules, which can evolve depending on the actions of patients and therapists, as well as the needs of the task (for example the level of difficulty). Some parameters associated to these behaviours can be tuned according to the experience of the VAs with patients. For instance, a rower can have a predefined paddling style (frequency, ...) that can be modulated to deal with the patients' typical movements. Such adaptive behaviour during the exergame can be consolidated potentially through a learning strategy, so that the default behaviour is more adequate to a given population, with the possibility for the therapist to overload those self-tuned parameters.</p> <p>To this end, all nodes will have to collect and use both local information, and the result of the actions performed by the rest of the involved agents to adapt their strategy.</p> <p>Beyond the VAs acting as patients, there will be VAs controlled by a specific module in the game, which is in charge of guessing the group behaviour, insert attractors and distractors, etc. Some learning could be implemented also at this level, with very simple AI models, to optimise the recognition of situations and the selection of the proper element to instantiate in order to overcome the situation.</p> <p>NOTE: Evolution and learning capabilities of the VAs are not the primary goal of this assessment scenario. Depending on the level of maturity of the project technologies at M18 and their adoption within the Use Case, the possibility of transferring some learning approaches developed for the MIRTO cognitive engine at the UC level may be exploited.</p>

<p>Technical Constraints</p>	<p>Very low latency: Visual feedback requires less than 50 ms in collaborative virtual environments, halved for haptic feedback and further reduced as the number of participants grows, as latencies introduce cross-effects. <i>Message latency:</i> < 50 ms</p> <p>Bandwidth capacity: It limits the number of participants locally represented in the virtual space. <i>Network bandwidth:</i> min 100 kbps per player, desiderate 1 Mbps per player</p> <p>Power/Energy: Low-power near-sensor processing and edge-to-fog data exchange.</p> <p>Frame per second (FPS): Most video games today are developed to hit a frame rate of 60 FPS, but anywhere between 30 FPS and 60 FPS is considered acceptable. That's not to say that games cannot exceed 60 FPS, many do, but for anything below 30 FPS, animations may become choppy and show a lack of fluid motion. <i>Frame duration:</i> min 16.67 ms (60 FPS)</p>
<p>UC Evaluation</p>	
<p>Baseline</p>	<p>Qualitative baseline:</p> <p>Collaborative rehabilitation systems allow people with motor, cognitive and neurological deficits to perform recovery protocols in a stimulating environment, populated by subjects who can play different roles (patients, doctors/physiotherapists, family members, etc). The paramount value of this paradigm lies in the scientific evidence that subjects have a much higher performance if they interact with a partner, even intermittently, than those who perform the exercise alone. Both partners' performance and the nature of their behaviour influence both cognitive and motor improvements and can provide neuromotor adaptations in interacting humans, even when they are unaware of the partner's presence.</p> <p>The current state of the art in collaborative training aimed at rehabilitation is intended for pairs of individuals, typically patient-therapists. Only one multiplayer setup has been found in the scientific literature [TNG17], in which participants play in teams but each performing their own task independently (contributing individually to their team's score, but not cooperating in a collaborative task); furthermore, in this exercise the patient is required to perform reaching movements for a cognitive rehabilitation exercise based on an association image-writing rehabilitation pattern. This, at a motor level, can also be used to perform basic training for the upper limb. Also, player satisfaction with real-time multiplayer games is correlated with performance of the communications network. The network is the most dynamic component of such games; congestion and channel loss figure prominently in achieving bounds required for real-time response. If messages cannot be delivered on-time, game developers must use predictive techniques to maintain the game experience.</p> <p>The ability to tune this prediction with in-context measurements allows game developers to tune their prediction model for network conditions rather than designing around a single assumed level of network quality, thereby delivering even more convincing real-time experiences.</p> <p>Quantitative Baseline:</p> <p>Evaluation KPIs to measure:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>User's acceptance/system usability:</i> e.g., Simulator Sickness Questionnaire (<10), System Usability Scale (>70%).

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Treatment effectiveness</i> (on healthy volunteers): e.g., verification of the interactive initiative (exploration of motor strategy, by varying motor performance in terms of speed, fluidity, etc), evaluation of the effectiveness of the collaboration (task completion, completion time). There's no quantitative baseline value as the application is completely novel.
Expectation and needs	<p>Scalability: it is necessary to use a multiplayer approach based on the creation of small groups, with a variable size from 2 to 6 players per group, to ensure that all participants play an active role in the collaborative task and that the coordination of participants is always efficient and stable. However, multiple groups can share the same playground, so that a global behaviour can be pursued.</p> <p>Adaptivity: the evolution of both the scenario and the collaborative task and the computational workload associated with them is variable, since it depends on the number of participants, on the number of the active nodes operating in a certain area of the virtual environment at a given time, on the approaches of artificial intelligence used to model (and possibly evolve) the behaviours of VAs, on the activation/deactivation of some computational resources, and on the number of sensors and actuators used at a given moment.</p> <p>Cooperativeness: this scenario is a system of systems, since each patient/therapist node is a system that includes a body network of physiological/biomechanical sensors and is part of a cluster of nodes, which in turn is a system, which can also interact with the other clusters.</p> <p>Dependability: the system protects the management of sensitive data. No relevant physiological signals will be shared by the system.</p> <p>Qualitative goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Collaborative rehabilitation training used by more than 2 people at the same time without appreciable latency issues; • Collaborative rehabilitation training involving both physical patients and VAs; • Collaborative rehabilitation paradigm based on local information and visual-haptic interaction only, following for example swarm intelligence principles; • Possibility of integrating in the virtual experience information coming from multiple unconventional sensors in real-time; • Low latency game server for an effective user experience. <p>Quantitative goals:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Increase of 50% of the number of physical and/or virtual actors involved in a collaborative rehabilitation training at the same time (more than 2 people); • Successful integration in the game of at least 3 VAs; • Reduction in the frequency of prediction algorithms intervention due to high latency >20%.

3.2 Mobility Use Case - Intersection Safety

Use Case (UC) Title
UC identity data

UC Owner	TNO
Involved Partners	<p>TNO: TNO coordinates with the municipality of Helmond (NL) for a physical installation of the infrastructure of the use case and demonstrator. TNO connects the infrastructure to cloud services for traffic information and provides a Connected Cooperative Automated Mobility (CCAM) test vehicle to cooperate with the roadside infrastructure.</p> <p>CRF: CRF provides smart cameras (edge devices), computing devices (fog) and traffic monitoring/controlling services that make use of camera images and use and produce V2X messages.</p>
Application Domain	Smart Mobility / Traffic Safety

UC overview

Application diagram
(Note that the high-quality version of this diagram is attached in Appendix 2)

Application Diagram description

This UC demonstrates the capabilities and benefits of a 360-orchestration in the cloud-to-edge continuum when applied to monitoring, analysing, and influencing mobility systems. It takes place in an urban, traffic-intensive crossing in the city of Helmond. The traffic lights at the crossing are augmented with smart cameras, edge devices, SW services, and communication devices able to (see blocks in the schema):

- **“Detect and track vehicles”** using:
 - Information from traffic light controllers via cooperative awareness messages (CAM)
 - Information from service providers
 - Information from cooperative vehicles using CAM messages
 - Installed cameras
- **“Detect and track Vulnerable Road Users (VRUs)”** using:
 - Information from traffic light controllers
 - Installed cameras
- **“Estimate the risk of collisions”** between VRUs and vehicles.
- **“Warn vehicles”** in case of risk of collisions by sending Collaborative Perception Messages (CPM) to cooperative vehicles, for example for VRUs that are about to cross the intersection

These are the 4 main activities around which the UC revolves and are related to the primary domain application (traffic safety).

Moreover, the system infrastructure will offer an additional functionality (via the MYRTUS computing continuum approach), namely **“orchestrate**

[computation task](#)", that is responsible for orchestrating execution among resources.

The smart cameras to be used offer a base set of resources (memory, computing power, network bandwidth, etc.) able to accommodate some of the processing and communication services. In some modes of operation, e.g. when the flow of actors in the crossing is not intense or just few services are active, the resources offered by the camera and edge devices might be enough. In these modes, SW services are orchestrated to run mainly at the edge. This minimises data transmission in the network, reduces the overall latency in the system response, and reduces global power consumption of the system (in particular in the fog).

On other modes of operation, e.g. when the flow of actors in the crossing is intense, making detection more difficult, or when many processing services are required to run concurrently, the resources offered at the edge become scarce and congested. This is often a reason for instability in the system, larger response times, and eventually failure of some or all the services. In this UC, we offer the possibility to (seamlessly) orchestrate these services into resources offered in a cloud infrastructure or neighbouring edge facility. To do that, this UC (see blocks in the schema above) will:

- Implement monitoring mechanisms that detect possible changes in the mode of operation of the system (see ["compute handover need"](#) block in the schema). For example, detect a significant increase in detected object density or a lower visibility which means a more efficient model is needed (note that detection might become trickier when objects overlap each other).
- Implement triggers for orchestrating services and SW modules into a new configuration that offers similar functionality but with guaranteed stability (see ["compute handover need"](#) block in the schema).
- Use learning-based orchestration mechanisms able to optimise the use of resources, learn successful orchestration strategies from past usage (see ["lean orchestration procedure"](#) block in the schema).
- Execute the actual handover of the computation task (either horizontal or vertical, see ["handover computation task"](#) block in the schema).
- Consider the transmission of private or sensitive data during the orchestration of services. To protect privacy when transmitting images on the network (depending on the selected operational mode), a privacy protection module (detecting and blurring selectively people's faces and vehicle licence plates in the images) is meant to be adopted. When transmitting messages to vehicles (CPM, warnings) no markers allowing identification of a user are included.

<p>Deployment Diagram (Note that the high-quality version of this diagram is attached in Appendix 2)</p>	
<p>Deployment Diagram description</p>	<p>The deployment diagram depicts our current view on the different resources that will be offered by the system and how the services are – in principle – organised in them. The diagram shows main SW blocks of the traffic safety use case, without detailing the SW components necessary for orchestration, which will be included in version2 of the deliverable (result is WP2), showing also the different MIRTO aspects of the system. The current version presents:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • the different components of the infrastructure: devices (in blue) and services (light orange and yellow) for this use case and application. • examples of deployment of the services into the infrastructure: such as: <i>Video Streaming</i> and <i>Image Capture</i> are services grounded in the <i>Edge Devices</i>. • MIRTO agents (not shown in this picture but expected to be there in the final deployment) will be included at each layer: agents follow similar internal architecture and interfaces. However, their implementation is layer specific or specific to the cluster of devices they manage. MIRTO agents, in perspective, will have an interface to share and collect information on the (distributed) MYRTUS Knowledge Base. <p>The services from the UC applications will be orchestrated to run in different devices or layers. Such orchestration is driven by a) requirements imposed by the application, b) events such as availability of resources or c) optimization requests (load balancing needs), etc. So, for example, an increase in the number of pedestrians and cars in the crossing can cause the service <i>collision, detection & vehicle warning</i> to be run in the <i>Cloud Server</i> instead of in the <i>Road side unit (RSU)</i>.</p>
<p>Offered services</p>	<p>For participants of the traffic system:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Stable and reliable information about the traffic conditions in the area, even when usage conditions are changing (such as more intense traffic, exceptional behaviour, failure in parts of the system, etc); • Timely information about dangerous situations; • Sharing of traffic information with cooperative vehicles, enabling more safety in cooperative vehicles. <p>For traffic controllers and traffic regulators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Consistent coverage, and timely and reliable information at all times, mitigating lack of information or degradation of the information due to overload in the system, congestion, failure in part of the infrastructure, etc.

	<p>For services and resources providers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Flexibility and adaptability in the deployment of their services, reducing dependency on the availability of particular resources, service or information providers, etc; ● Ability to optimise the usage of resources and energy consumption to the situation at hand and current demands.
Expected human role	<p>Real-time and online communication of safety-related traffic information to cooperative vehicles and other actors allows them to participate in the traffic in a more situational-aware way. Being able to offer these services in a reliable way in varying conditions (changing flow intensity, large number of operating services, etc.) and increase the trust in these systems and influences the behaviour of traffic participants.</p> <p>Moreover, the UC per-se offers many long-term human-relevant benefits:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● More reliable and more stable traffic information to the municipality and traffic controllers. This allows regulators to make better decisions and influence the mobility system in a more effective way. ● The ability to orchestrate and scale resources and services in an energy-aware manner reduces the energetic and carbon footprint of the systems.
UC Requirements	
Requested functionalities	<p>The baseline for the application software in this UC consists of:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. a computer vision system composed of video acquisition modules (directly bound to each camera). Images are provided to the processing upstream via a service endpoint. 2. a pipeline for image processing modules. Services and modules in the pipeline include, but are not limited to, object detectors, bounding box annotation, object recognition, object blurring etc. <ol style="list-style-type: none"> a. The camera embedded modules are built based on open-source Axis ACAP SDK and examples¹. b. An example of an open-source detection model for the camera². 3. communication modules broadcasting or providing the information produced in the pipeline to consumers. Examples are messages being broadcast to vehicles in the crossing about maps of detected road users and vehicles (CPM) and warnings on possible dangerous situations (Decentralised Environmental Notification Message, DENM). <p>Points 1 to 3 above are functionalities at the application domain level. They must conform to some requirements on, for example, latency for messages, image processing throughput according to the number of identifiable elements, energy minimization, etc. To keep up with these requirements, the system should be able to adapt the deployment of computing resources.</p>
Expected Operating modes - User Stories	<p>Pedestrians and cyclists are VRUs. In traffic crossings, pedestrians and cyclists rely mostly on their observation skills and on the traffic lights as elements of signalization for danger, such as vehicles approaching, traffic jams, etc. Using cameras in traffic crossings, it is possible to detect and track road users (vehicles, motorbikes, bicycles, and pedestrians). Web and IoT services using the images of these cameras and other sensors can analyse</p>

¹ <https://github.com/AxisCommunications/acap-computer-vision-sdk-examples>

² https://github.com/google-coral/edgetpu/raw/master/test_data/ssd_mobilenet_v2_coco_quant_postprocess.tflite

	<p>and predict dangerous situations, such as imminent collision. A flexible, scalable, and seamless deployment of these services is the background of this UC. VRUs of the traffic system can be warned via sound systems (speakers) or “navigation” apps about imminent danger. <i>Though this is not envisioned to be provided in the UC scenario, this possibility is real.</i></p> <p>Other users of the traffic system are also involved. Traffic controllers (human or automatic) can use results of the detection analysis and warnings of the services to initiate actions that alleviate the traffic, re-route traffic etc. Vehicles equipped with special equipment may also receive warnings for dangerous situations or suggestions to avoid the crossing of intersections. In one of the scenarios explored, an assisted vehicle will receive messages from the traffic analysis services.</p> <p>In all the described cases, it is important that the whole loop of detection, analysis, and warnings happens in a timely and accurate manner. And this timely and accurate response should be respected independently on how the services are deployed -- in the near edge, fog, cloud, or distributed among these layers. Users of the traffic system should not notice significant differences in response time nor accuracy of the services in any set up.</p> <p>MYRTUS smart mobility application scenario is meant to demonstrate the use of simple detection and analysis services that are enablers for such more complex use of the proposed technologies. After discussions with external partners (e.g. the city administration of Helmond) and internal partners (TNO, CRF), the use case will not contain elements of controlling the traffic (such as influencing traffic lights, etc.) nor warning signals (e.g. board or sound system). This is because the use of those elements adds an additional layer of security measures and liability risks. Nonetheless, the warnings generated by the UC services will be visible for the MYRTUS team for assessment and demonstration purposes.</p>
<p>Expected Operating modes - System Expected Behaviour behind the User Stories</p>	<p><i>[Please note that three different modes of operation are described below, but they are not user dependent. There are no different operating modes for the pedestrians and cyclists (users of the system), nor the (assisted) vehicles. For them, it should be only relevant that the quality and timeliness of the messages is not affected by the orchestration of the services in the background.]</i></p> <p>In operational mode 1, all processing tasks, including frame capture, road user detection, and message generation, are executed independently within each camera. This decentralised approach is highly power-efficient and well-suited for periods of low traffic and for services that do not require the fusion and tracking of objects detected by different cameras.</p> <p>As traffic increases towards rush hour, the camera-embedded models might become insufficient for detecting overlapping road users. The system now needs extra resources outside of the edge. This is also the case when fusion and tracking services between cameras are necessary. In these cases, the system can switch to operational mode 2. In this mode, while detection and geo-mapping may continue to be performed individually by each camera, the detection results are transmitted to processing units in the</p>

	<p>fog/cloud. These units perform the fusion of detections, analyse them, and generate message payloads for vehicles and pedestrians. Although this mode incurs a slight increase in latency and power consumption at the fog layer, it maintains good levels of privacy and network load efficiency.</p> <p>In more complex situations, the system can switch to operational mode 3. In this mode, cameras stream video data to the fog, where more robust and efficient detection models handle the detection process. While this increases fog power consumption and network load, it ensures stable detection throughput rates.</p> <p>In all operational modes, there is the possibility of orchestration. In operational mode 1, even if the resources are more local, there can be changes in the algorithms used, the sampling rate, etc., all driven to optimise the system KPIs, while guaranteeing the functional constraints (e.g. detection accuracy, etc.). In operational modes 2 and 3, the resources and services can be freely shuffled to achieve better system efficiency, while respecting application constraints and deployment constraints.</p> <p>By introducing these three operational modes, the availability of the services will be guaranteed to end users, even when the traffic density is very high.</p>
<p>Evolution and Learning capabilities</p>	<p>The emphasis on the evolution and learning capabilities will mainly serve two purposes:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● orchestrating the system within one mode of operation to achieve better KPIs (e.g. power consumption), while complying with application constraints and user requirements. The MIRTO cognitive engine behind system execution can learn which system configurations should be used for optimising certain KPIs. ● orchestrating the transition between operational modes. The optimal timing and strategy for orchestrating resources during operational mode transitions is not predetermined. Therefore, it offers an opportunity for learning. <p>Learning and evolution can be based also on internal or external factors, that is, based on two sort of indicators:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Triggering mode switching and guiding orchestration via generic computing indicators, such as energy consumption and network load. ● Triggering mode switching and guiding orchestration via application-specific indicators, such as number of detections needed per frame, etc. <p>In the first approach, mode switching is triggered, and resources are re-organized according to generic computing indicators such as CPU load, available memory, time of day, day of the week, increase of network throughput, etc. The system will learn the normal variations of these indicators over time and the impact of mode switching on them. This method does not utilise any application-generated data, like measured traffic density, to decide the timing for switching modes or how to (re-)allocate resources. This method can eventually also include learning the relationship between system setups and their performance, energy consumption, etc. The second approach uses application-specific indicators, such as measured traffic density or the number of VRUs. When combined</p>

	<p>with the generic indicators from the first approach, this method can provide a more precise estimate for the optimal timing of mode switching. By integrating both types of indicators, the system can enhance its decision-making process for mode transitions, ensuring more efficient and effective resources management and service availability/quality.</p>
<p>Technical Constraints</p>	<p>The following technical requirements must be respected:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1 Maximal time delay (latency): the time it takes from detection to concluding a dangerous situation exists must not be too long (1s max between detection and alert reception by a vehicle). 2 Communication bandwidth: the bandwidth needed for streaming (multiple) cameras should be sufficient (25 Mbps per camera). 3 Computational power: enough computer power must be available to detect road users in real-time (the image processing throughput should be at least 10 frames per seconds at 720p resolution). <p>Moreover, for the implementation of the UC, some additional constraints may also be present, such as:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. The amount of computing resources (e.g. memory, processor, etc.) in cameras are determined by their off-the-shelf configuration. 2. There are often a limited number of network channels to access some resources. Services will be forced to share them. 3. Physical limitations for installing additional HW at the edge. Example, if HW should be included in road cabinets, they should follow strict rules on size and energy consumption. 4. Electrical power: max 25W per camera (due to PoE). <p>These constraints will be considered while integrating the demonstrator in WP9-10.</p>
<p>UC Evaluation</p>	
<p>Baseline</p>	<p>Qualitative baseline:</p> <p>The baseline system consists of individually operating cameras, each with their own computer vision system and all image processing modules running on the host camera. This limits the detection quality to object detections and simple tracking within the field of view of a single camera. The privacy of people and vehicles is also protected in video recording and streaming in the baseline system.</p> <p>There is no tracking or conflict detection over multiple cameras. Road users are not tracked over the complete intersection and between intersections. Standard algorithms for detection and tracking are deployed that fit within the resources available on a single camera. In heavy road traffic situations, delays will occur in the detections and warnings.</p> <p>External vehicle information from roadside units and cloud services will not be communicated and fused with camera detections to increase the situational awareness beyond the camera view and improve detection performance within camera view.</p> <p>Traffic light information will not be communicated to the camera detection systems, e.g. to determine red-light violations.</p> <p>Quantitative Baseline:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● The system will be restricted in: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ device resources: limited CPU, GPU, memory; ○ device constraints: temperature, power consumption;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ network bandwidth; ○ Scale - number of objects and visibility conditions for scene analysis; ○ Adaptivity - traffic situation: accident, dangerous situation, emergency vehicle are not detected. ○ Cooperativeness - no object detection and tracking over the entire intersection and between intersections ○ Dependability - conflict detection is only possible within camera view ● The system performance will be restricted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ application result quality: recall, precision; ○ size of the area of detection; ○ latency, frequency of the detection; ○ global power consumption.
Expectation and needs	<p>Scalability: With increased deployment of automated vehicles, processing, and communication needs increase more than linear.</p> <p>Adaptivity: The expected computational workload and communication data rates are variable and increase more than linear with the traffic volume and the number of road users. The system will adapt to new computation requirements by shifting services and network connections among the resources. Usability of the system -- such as timely response, and quality of service offered -- should not drop below given levels of acceptance.</p> <p>Cooperativeness: Object detection, (re-)identification and tracking are improved by collaboration of roadside cameras and vehicle sensors. E.g. vehicles improve detection/tracking/situation awareness of VRUs/vehicles using roadside messages. Roadside cameras and vehicle-based sensors track objects using signal timing information from the traffic light controllers as well as CCAM messages to assess potential conflicts such as red-light violation warnings.</p> <p>Dependability: Detection performance is critical for hazard warning, collaborative perception and manoeuvre coordination and detection errors may directly result in safety hazards. Moreover, in general, in this scenario secure communication paths should be guaranteed.</p> <p>Qualitative goals: The system should adapt dynamically to the varying conditions (dynamic selection of services adapted to scene of variable difficulty in various traffic conditions) while optimising the quality of the results.</p> <p>Quantitative goals: Latency: The time-to-warning should be:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● below 1 seconds, if the warning is issued for pedestrians and cyclists. ● below 0.5 seconds, if the warning is issued for assisted vehicles. ● below 3 minutes, if the warning is an analysis of the intensity of traffic in the crossing and used by the traffic controlling team. <p>Image processing throughput: the system should be able to analyse and detect road users from at least 10 FPS for each camera at the intersection. For better positioning of road users when the scene is more difficult to analyse, an increased frequency of 20 FPS for some cameras could be available.</p>

	<p>Energy consumption: Displacement of services in various platforms should enable the decrease in energy consumption (globally for the system) of about 10% between different configurations.</p>
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4 MYRTUS Computing Continuum Approach

Starting from the assumption that:

- T.CH1 – Centralised computing solutions struggle to meet scalable and low-latency application scenarios, as well as privacy-related matters. Data exposure can improve learning and decision-making processes but may violate data protection regulations/laws. On the contrary, edge computing helps solving those latter problems with proximity, but hardly satisfies intense computing and storage requirements.
- T.CH2 – Cloud, edge and end-devices are currently handled as different isolated silos, preventing an application to be seamlessly deployed and dynamically updated for continuous optimization, strategic to foster a sustainable computing approach, across continuum.
- T.CH3 – The more a system is heterogeneous, complex, and required to be adaptive, the more it is likely for designers to rely on partially integrated toolchains/methodologies tuned for specific aspects. Frameworks and tools are there, but effective interoperability is still to be reached.

MYRTUS, as specified in the Grant Agreement, aims at:

- T.OBJ1 - defining a **reference infrastructure** where a **diversity of fog-level and edge-level devices converge with the cloud** to form a computing continuum capable of addressing the needs of complex and dynamic systems, including CPS with a living dimension.
- T.OBJ2 - featuring a **360° dynamic runtime orchestration scheme**, embodied within the **MIRTO AI-powered cognitive engine**, to guarantee high performance and energy efficiency, preserving security and trust.
- T.OBJ3 - providing a **reference design and programming environment** for continuum computing systems, featuring **interoperable support for cross-layer modelling, threat analysis, design space exploration, application modelling, components synthesis, and code generation**.

Our goals perfectly match the motivation and goals of the EUCloudEdgeIoT.eu Initiative³ (EU-CEI), which claims that *the concept of Continuum has emerged as being more than the sum of cloud, edge and IoT functionalities, breaking boundaries among the different computing layers moving the computation from the device to the farthest data centre, and vice versa, according to both application needs and availability of resources*. The EU-CEI aims to define a common coordinated design and development strategy for Cloud, Edge and IoT Continuum *bringing together and promoting the cooperation between research projects, developers and suppliers, business users, and potential adopters of the continuum computing paradigm*. One of the technical goals of the EU-CEI is to *define a reference architecture for the continuum to be promoted as a standard and mapped with the solutions architectures of newly funded projects operating in continuum areas, such as MYRTUS*.

Therefore, being already aligned both in terms of topics and goals, in the first month of the project, during the specification and requirements phase within T1.2, we decided to align MYRTUS technical pillars' contribution to the EU-CEI initiative. We started by framing the **MYRTUS reference infrastructure** (MYRTUS technical pillar 1, WP3 and WP4 activities) and **MIRTO cognitive engine** (MYRTUS technical pillar 2, WP5 and WP6 activities) with respect to the EU-CEI reference architecture. Please note that there cannot be a complete distinction among blocks that are relevant just for the infrastructure and blocks relevant just for the cognitive engine. For example, in terms of Resource Management and Orchestration you need specific support at the infrastructure level, e.g. Kubernetes, while at the cognitive engine level, in combination with the Artificial Intelligence blocks, decisions for orchestrating the tasks over resources will be taken. Moreover, even if mainly in an indirect manner, the activities to be

³ <https://eucloudedgeiot.eu/>

carried out in the **MYRTUS Design and Programming Environment** (MYRTUS technical pillar 3, WP7 and WP8 activities) are relevant to map and implement the expected building blocks. EU-CEI has identified eight categories representing the *technical processes to operate applications along the continuum*. These categories represent the building blocks of a continuum computing infrastructure and are summarised in Table 4-1 hereafter along with MYRTUS envisioned strategies that will implement them.

Table 4-1- EU-CEI Building Blocks versus their MYRTUS envisioned implementation

EU-CEI BUILDING BLOCKS AND DEFINITIONS	MYRTUS ENVISIONED IMPLEMENTATION
<p>Security & Privacy - Mechanisms for secure data and transactions between different Components.</p>	<p>We intend to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Implement authorization and authentication mechanisms of users and resources; •Support data integrity and availability, guaranteeing trustable, accessible, and coherent data exchange. •Provide secure communication schemes, by means of encrypted transactions. •Provide system integrity enabling design time threat analysis and defining trust-related KPIs to be used at runtime to implement trust and reputation schemes.
<p>Trust & Reputation - Models for allowing users of a continuum platform to generate trust in providers or increase their reputation (mainly in federated models).</p>	
<p>Data management - It includes collection, storage, and any other type of action performed over data.</p>	<p>Data related functionalities, storage and processing capabilities are layer/component dependent. In Section 4.1 an update of MYRTUS reference infrastructure and its components is presented.</p>
<p>Resource management - It entails management of physical infrastructures and individual devices.</p>	<p>At the infrastructure level, Kubernetes will be used as a low-level orchestrator, with LIQO (ARK) on top to achieve seamless virtualization of the underlying infrastructure. While at runtime MIRTO cognitive engine covers the high-level orchestrator role. Its goal is to handle scalability without compromising Quality of Service and heterogeneity (one cognitive engine architecture with target-dependent implementations). Aligned with the EU-CEI vision, the MIRTO optimization goals include latency reduction, throughput increase, and improved reliability without sacrificing security, privacy and trust. Additionally, MIRTO aims to reduce energy consumption as well. Please note that MYRTUS Design and Programming Environment will produce the Cloud Service Archive (CSAR) archive to enable the deployment on the continuum infrastructure, exporting also meta-information (e.g. characterization of the available operating points, model-level information of microservices for re-optimization purposes) to seamlessly integrate with the MIRTO cognitive engine and facilitate runtime management.</p>
<p>Orchestration - Distributions of workloads, data or resources for executing a given action.</p>	

<p>Network - Connectivity considerations, including private networks and activities such as network slicing.</p>	<p>We aim at:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Defining a multi-layer infrastructure set-up: with common interfaces and exchange protocols. This means, for example, that to foster seamless Workload (WL) balance at runtime, the different edge and fog components will embed a set of identical interfaces. •Enabling MIRTO cognitive engine to carry out network resource management, where possible, to balance load and latency.
<p>Monitoring & Observability - It is intended at infrastructure level, including telemetry, and service/application level.</p>	<p>In line with EU-CEI monitors classification we foresee:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •<i>Application monitoring</i>: status of the application to identify underperformance issues not related to network/ devices. •<i>Telemetry monitoring</i>: connectivity status and information loss. •<i>Infrastructure and Resource monitoring</i>: status of the components. <p>Observability will be implemented by the MIRTO cognitive engine leveraging the distributed knowledge-based to make smart decisions.</p>
<p>Artificial Intelligence - It is expected to be embedded in most of the activities performed.</p>	<p>MIRTO cognitive engine will adopt Swarm-Intelligence and Federated Learning to master WLs and resources orchestration at runtime.</p>

Here follows the update, with respect to the Grant Agreement, on MYRTUS specific core technologies. In these first months we focussed first on defining the main characteristics and capabilities of each individual pillar. Indeed, as it can be noticed in the introduction of Section 4.1, Section 4.2 and Section 4.3, the overview of each pillar has been refined with respect to the original description, detailing the internal architecture. We already identified the interfaces that will have to be further investigated and discussed:

- MYRTUS infrastructure and MIRTO cognitive engine “share” information. The monitored data are intended to be stored in a distributed knowledge base, which will be exploited by MIRTO cognitive engine agents to make informed decisions. Therefore, in the next few months, as part of WP3, we have to finalise a decision about which knowledge base to adopt, how data is stored there, and how MIRTO, on WP5 side, is assessing them.
- MIRTO cognitive engine represents the high-level AI-based orchestrator, which exploits LIQO to guarantee seamless virtualization of the underlying infrastructure. LIQO leverages the native Kubernetes low level orchestrator. Provided that all WP3 components that will have to be included in the continuum are already meant to support Kubernetes, it is yet to be defined, as part of WP5 activities, the interface between MIRTO and the deployment infrastructure itself.
- MYRTUS DPE is responsible for creating the Deployment Specification that will be used to feed the MIRTO cognitive engine to orchestrate WLs and resources. Modelio tool, as part of WP7 activities, is already under extension to be able to create the Cloud Service Archive (.csar) package, which will contain all relevant TOSCA templates, scripts and files needed to allow WLs deployment and management in Kubernetes-based environments. This package is meant to also include relevant metadata information to manage available edge-

node level operating points. Complete package specification and how to include all the design-time to run-time information is still under discussion in WP7.

- Finally, the technologies to implement the container image registry and resource registry, that will have to be accessed by MIRTO to make its decisions, are still under discussion and evaluation in WP3.

At WP level, from September 2024 on, these activities will continue in dedicated working groups, with the goal of having a second refinement of this initial specification, at WP level, by the end of the year to guarantee a smooth technology development.

4.1 Pillar 1 - MYRTUS computing continuum infrastructure

Pillar 1 in a Nutshell

Technical Challenge: Centralised computing solutions struggle to meet scalable and low-latency application scenarios, and privacy-related matters. Data exposure can improve learning and decision-making processes but may violate data protection regulations. On the contrary, edge computing helps to address security and privacy with proximity, but hardly satisfies intense computing and storage requirements.

Technical Objective: MYRTUS defines a reference infrastructure where a diversity of fog-level and edge-level devices converge with the cloud to form a computing continuum capable of addressing the needs of complex and dynamic systems, including CPS with a living dimension.

Key Enabling Technology: MYRTUS onion-like computing continuum reference infrastructure will represent the enabler for seamless optimal execution of complex computational workflows across a heterogeneous continuum, in an energy-efficient and trustworthy manner.

Figure 4-1 - MYRTUS onion-like computing continuum reference infrastructure [Grant Agreement, Part B page 7]

The high-level overview of **MYRTUS onion-like reference infrastructure**, depicted in Figure 4-1 hasn't changed with respect to the Grant Agreement. It is built as a composable layered cloud-fog-edge computing continuum, integrating heterogeneous, autonomous, federated and collaborative computing components. Nonetheless, in the first months of WP3 we have worked into **refining its requirements and expected functionalities**, drafting its expected **generic architecture** (see Figure 4-2) and refining the **interface** with respect to the MIRTO cognitive engine.

MYRTUS computing continuum reference infrastructure.

Figure 4-2 - MYRTUS onion-like computing continuum reference infrastructure refined architecture

MYRTUS reference infrastructure is built as a composable layered cloud-fog-edge computing continuum, integrating heterogeneous, autonomous, federated and collaborative computing nodes. Edge devices will be tightly coupled to fog nodes that have, in turn, high availability connection to cloud. As described above the reference infrastructure provides *seamless execution of complex computational workflows across a heterogeneous continuum of connected computational resources*.

- The edge layer consists of commercial off-the-shelf (COTS) multicores, Heterogeneous Multiprocessor Systems-on-Chip (HMPSoCs) Field Programmable Gate Arrays (**FPGA**)-based accelerators and adaptive RISC-V processors with custom computing units providing complex computation including AI algorithms. It supports Kubernetes for the orchestration mechanism and will have an interface to communicate with MIRTO agents.
- The Fog layer consists of **Fog Micro Data Centres (FMDCs)** and **smart gateways** to provide analytics services on medium to long term data and also to extend the capabilities of edge devices. For the workload deployments, Fog layer will support Kubernetes and will have an interface to communicate with MIRTO agents. MIRTO agents at Fog can communicate with edge-cloud agents as well as with other fog agents providing 360 runtime orchestration.
- The cloud layer provides long term storage, subsystem monitoring, coordination, data mining and historical analysis which complies with **Gaia-X trust model**.

All the components at each layer will have their specific interface to communicate with the layer's specific MIRTO agent which, in turn, communicates with the other layers' MIRTO agent. All **layers share one ontological knowledge base** (logical view), which can be distributed in different layers (implementation view). This way, data remains close to their consumers, but can be shared between layers for analysis and decision making.

Most of the EU-CEI building blocks are going to be implemented and supported basically in all the layers of the proposed infrastructure, in a target-dependent manner.

1. **Security & Privacy, Trust & Reputation** - Mechanisms for secure data and transactions between different computing nodes, as well as to guarantee components authentication, will be implemented. Three different levels of security are currently envisioned, as

reported in Table 4-2, and will be implemented/supported according to a minimal set of requirements provided by USI. The type of computation as well as the orchestration will be determined by the level of trust of the component. Moreover, TNO is going to provide an interface towards cloud and fog, compatible with the Gaia-X trust model.

2. **Data Management** - Figure 4-1 already specifies what is expected in terms of storage and processing from the different MYRTUS reference infrastructure layers. Within the project four different components are expected to be developed/improved: two at the edge (namely the HMPSoC accelerators from UNISS and UNICA, and the customizable RISC-V processor from UPM) and two at the fog layer (namely the smart gateway from ABI and the FMDC from HIRO). At the edge, local storage in main memory and ad-hoc, flexible, coprocessing is going to be guaranteed by UNISS and UNICA and UPM accelerators. While, at the fog layer, the two components of ABI and HIRO differ from the availability of storage and the processing capabilities. ABI smart gateway acts normally as a hub for data exchange among a diversity of actors at the edge (e.g., sensors, actuators, HW accelerators, etc.) and the cloud, and supports light local processing; whereas the FMDC provides edge services software stack to support for big data processing. With respect to HW, the FMDC provides disaggregated, heterogenous, hyper converged servers, high performing, and energy efficient (Power Usage Effectiveness 1.03). The FMDC will be responsible for communication between cloud and edge layer. It will primarily respond to data flows and take action on the data based on their relevance and prioritisation in the edge layer. On top of that, it will timely feed information and insights from the fog and cloud applications to the edge devices.
3. **Resource Management and Orchestration** - At the reference infrastructure level, low level orchestration mechanisms are meant to be enabled to WLS offloading to layers/devices. Edge devices (UNISS and UNICA, UPM) already leverage a linux-based OS capable of running Kubernetes, which is already supported also by the FMDC. ABI gateway has already planned to add such support, which should be straightforward. Indeed, the lightweight YOCTO-based OS integrated in the HMPSoC accelerators from UNISS and UNICA is derived from Ability, the Linux embedded distribution of Abinsula. Therefore, porting back in the gateway the newly developed recipes supporting Kubernetes is expected to be fast.
4. **Monitoring and Observability** - Edge devices (UNISS and UNICA, UPM) are already instrumented to support basic runtime monitoring at the node level. It is based on Performance Monitoring Counters (PMCs) and information, like latency and energy, are expected to be used at least locally by the Node Manager within an instance of the MIRTO cognitive engine to self-adjusting the node configuration. Other relevant application and telemetry monitors are expected to be determined, as soon as the work at the manager level in Pillar 2 will progress. It is expected that, at minimum, execution-relevant metrics such as processing and communication latency, as well as energy consumption are retrieved also at the fog level. Nonetheless, we have envisioned also the definition of trust indicators to be computed and made available locally at runtime. Data and metrics, when relevant for horizontal and vertical orchestration of WLS to be carried out by the MIRTO cognitive engine agents, will be collected and retrieved using TOSCA data format. Observability will be enabled leveraging a shared knowledge base. We are currently considering the use of ETCD, which is a strongly consistent, distributed key-value store for data that needs to be accessed by a distributed system or cluster of machines and it is already part of the Kubernetes environment.
5. **Network** - Edge components are expected to connect to the continuum with standard protocols (through Linux libraries). As an example, the HMPSoC accelerators from UNISS and UNICA are already capable of establishing secure connections via HTTP with the ABI

gateway exchanging JSON packets. The gateway itself is extremely flexible in terms of connectivity interfaces, it is customizable with ad-hoc user defined interfaces, and already natively supports several protocols (e.g. HTTP, MQTT, etc.). The FMDC is designed to seamlessly integrate with various edge components, leveraging standard protocols to maintain secure and efficient communication channels. It supports a wide array of connectivity protocols such as HTTP, MQTT, CoAP, and more, providing flexibility and interoperability within the network.

6. **Artificial Intelligence** - computing nodes in all layers are already capable of running AI models of different complexity, which is mandatory to support the MIRTO agents that will be executed on the reference infrastructure to support the 360° orchestration.

Table 4-2 - MYRTUS envisioned security levels

	High	Medium	Low
Encryption	Symmetric encryption primitives which are PQC resistant, e.g. AES-256	Symmetric encryption primitives which may not be PQC resistant but are suitable for current security threats, e.g. AES-128	Symmetric encryption primitives which may not be PQC resistant but are suitable for current security threats and consider computational complexity of the node, e.g. ASCON-128
Authentication	Digital signature schemes which are PQC resistant, following the NIST standard (CRYSTALS-Dilithium, FALCON, and SPHINCS+)	Digital signature schemes which may not be PQC resistant but are suitable for current security threats, e.g. DSA, RSA, ECDSA	Digital signature schemes which may not be PQC resistant but are suitable for current security threats and consider computational complexity of the node, lightweight authentication schemes e.g. ECDSA
Key exchange	Key encapsulation mechanisms which are PQC resistant, following the NIST standard (CRYSTALS-KYBER)	Key encapsulation mechanisms which may not be PQC resistant but are suitable for current security threats, e.g. RSA	Key encapsulation mechanisms which may not be PQC resistant but are suitable for current security threats and consider computational complexity of the node, lightweight key exchange schemes e.g. ECDSA

Hashing	At least 512 size hash, e.g. SHA-512	At least 256 size hash, e.g. SHA-256	Lightweight hashing algorithms, considering the computational complexity of the node, e.g. ASCON-Hash, QUARK, spongent, photon
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4.1.1 Expected Results

In this section all the expected Pillar 1 results are refined with respect to the Grant Agreement description.

4.1.1.1 R1 – HMPSoCs accelerators

Identifier: R1		Partner: UNISS, UNICA	
Name: FPGA-based Heterogeneous Multi-Processor System on Chip accelerators			
Licence: 3-clause BSD	Owner: UNISS, UNICA	Contacts: francesca.palumbo@unica.it francesco.ratto@unica.it claudio.rubattu@uniss.it	
Short Description: HMPSoCs FPGA-based accelerators leveraging on open-source architectural templates and exploiting coarse-grained reconfigurable (CGR) approaches for edge computation.			
Baseline: Dataflow-based CGR accelerators provided by UNISS and UNICA can be used to achieve multi-tasking execution at the edge, which can be classified as functional multi-tasking (the accelerator can be reconfigured to execute the desired task) or trade-off-oriented multi-tasking (the accelerator can be reconfigured to set the desired implementation of the task). The same dataflow-based approach has been used also to implement AI acceleration at the edge leveraging a streaming approach.			TRL@M0: 3
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: At the architectural level, it is expected that these accelerators will evolve in different manners. First of all, the multi-tasking approach will be extended to support a combination of multi-tasking and multi-threading where needed. Moreover, the reconfiguration capabilities at the base of the CGR approaches are intended to be exploited to support approximate computing in the context of AI acceleration at the edge. Last, but not least, leveraging the heterogeneity of the chosen reference target, a customised version of the Abinsula Yocto-based Embedded Linux Distribution (Ability) will be used to allow edge-fog connection.			TRL@M36: 5
Plans and Expectation			
Assessment Plan@M18: Extensive lab assessment on traditional edge computing kernels, including (but not limited to) AES encryption/decryption, FFT, and video/Image processing kernels, will be carried out for the multi-threaded and multi-tasking accelerators. The AI at the edge capabilities will be assessed wrt common classification problems starting from MNIST and CIFAR-10. Metrics to be extracted will certainly involve processing latency, and power measurements, plus the accuracy for the AI at the edge accelerators, and the communication latency to connect to ABI's fog multi-sensor gateway .			

Expected Results@M18: Availability of the fog layer connection support. The accuracy of the AI at the edge accelerators, in the common classification problems, is expected to be in line with the other SoA approaches. Latency, throughput, and power improvements are case-specific, but we expect that the usage of HW-based edge acceleration approaches will allow us to save at least 10x latency reduction (wrt the embedded ARM cores) and to reach 20-30% of power dissipation reduction.

4.1.1.2 R2 – RISC-V processor with custom CGRA-based extensions

Identifier: R2		Partner: UPM
Name: RISC-V processor with custom CGRA-based extensions		
Licence: Solderpad Hardware Licence v2.1	Owner: UPM	Contacts: joseandres.otero@upm.es alfonso.rodruiguez@upm.es
Short Description: Multi-grain CGR Array (CGRA) tightly coupled with an open-source RISC-V processor through custom ISA extensions to support 1) automatic SW-to-HW code offloading using HW composition, 2) Edge AI capabilities in the RISC-V ecosystem.		
Baseline: A multigrain reconfigurable CGRA overlay for FPGAs loosely coupled with a host processor (Arm-based) via a standard memory-mapped interface. Support for a reduced set of integer arithmetic and logic operations within its core Processing Elements (PEs), and use of different granularity levels for FPGA reconfiguration (i.e., coarse to modify large chunks of the fabric, medium to compose regular 2D computing structures on the fabric, and fine to only modify LUT contents to change PE functionality).		TRL@M0: 3-4
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: Integration of the CGRA on the datapath of an open-source RISC-V processor core to provide hardware-accelerated custom ISA extensions as an alternative to the memory-mapped approach. Development of AI-oriented PEs (e.g., fixed- and floating-point arithmetic) and exploration of heterogeneous CGRA distributions (i.e., using different PEs in each position in the 2D grid, for instance to include internal scratchpad memories).		TRL@M36: 5
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: RTL simulation of the integrated CPU+CGRA computing infrastructure, using custom assembly instructions to properly exercise the accelerator with manually mapped application benchmarks (e.g., PolyBench). Synthesis and implementation on multiple FPGA devices, changing the spatial characteristics and capabilities of the CGRA.		
Expected Results@M18: Improved energy efficiency and performance metrics of the application benchmarks running on the CGRA fabric with hand-made mapping, which are to be assessed both at simulation level and on the target FPGA boards. Comparison of offloading overheads for both memory-mapped and extended-ISA flavours of the CGRA.		

4.1.1.3 R3 – Multi-Sensor Gateway

Identifier: R3		Partner: ABI
Name: Multi-Sensor Gateway		
Licence: GNU GPL	Owner: ABI	Contacts: tiziana.fanni@abinsula.com katuscia.zedda@abinsula.com

Short Description: The Multi-Sensor Gateway provides a unified management system, contributing to the secure and safe integration of a cooperative embedded system in a system-of-systems.

<p>Baseline: The gateway is based on the Abinsula Yocto-based Embedded Linux Distribution (Ability). It includes an edge part with light computation capabilities and a cloud part interfaces with an operator. It transparently manages the communication among the elements of the system and the operator. It supports different communication protocols (REST, MQTT, UDP, TCP, GRAPHQL, etc.) and accepts inputs described with custom-interfaces (data-interchange format). For each interface, a data converter module normalises the data interface, producing a standard JSON that can be sent to the cloud gateway. Main characteristics are: No vendor lock-in; No application specific; Generic and modular component; Main communication protocols; User-defined interfaces</p>	<p>TRL@M0: 4-5</p>
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<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: The strategy behind the evolution of the Multi-Sensor Gateway is based on two pillars: extend the communication capabilities (integrating new protocols) and improve the computation power (integrating a decision node in the gateway to trigger system reconfiguration and supporting the computation near sensor). We will extend its edge processing capabilities to support decision making and trigger (sub)-system reconfiguration.</p>	<p>TRL@M36: 6</p>
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Plans and Expectation

<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Simulations to verify flexibility with respect to the different interfaces and protocols required by other MYRTUS devices. Metrics are N of different communication protocols supported; N of different user-defined interfaces supported.</p>	<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Preliminary integration with edge devices, and verification of proper bidirectional communication.</p>
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<p>Expected Results@M18: N of different communication protocols supported: Baseline = 6; Goal >= 6.* N of different user-defined interfaces supported: Baseline = 5; Goal >= 5.</p>	<p>Expected Results@M18: Integration: Boolean Downlink communication: correctness of the message received. Uplink communication: correctness of device (re-)configuration</p>
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**Technical discussions are still ongoing to detail the required protocols and interfaces. Please, note that the minimum reached goal could be equal to the baseline, in case the new components to be connected to the gateway require protocols/interfaces that are already supported.*

4.1.1.4 R4 – Fog Micro Data Centre

Identifier: R4		Partner: HIRO
Name: Fog Micro Data Centre (FMDC)		
Licence: N.A.*	Owner: HIRO	Contacts: fred.buining@hiro-microdatacenters.nl veena.Rao@hiro-microdatacenters.nl rahul.Sharma@hiro-microdatacenters.nl sai.kireeti@hiro-microdatacenters.nl
Short Description: FMDCs guarantee: low-to-no processing latency; improved resiliency (no network loss) and security; cost savings (due to incremental deployment and composability) and scalability support.		
Baseline: An FMDC is a modular easy scalable data centre, small enclosures (1.8kW) up to shipping containers (500kW) with integrated power and cooling. Current features: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● <i>Software:</i> Edge services stack to support Big Data processing and AI applications ● <i>Hardware:</i> Industry standard, disaggregated, heterogenous, hyper converged servers. High performing, energy efficient PUE 1.03 and renewable compatible. ● <i>Intelligence:</i> operates fully autonomous, and its intelligence manages the collaboration with other EMDC's (East-West), 5G/6G and distant Cloud (North-South). ● <i>Reconfigurable:</i> Hardware and software components can be dynamically adjusted/restructured to meet changing computational demands or specific application requirements. ● <i>Performance:</i> optimal performance resilience and efficiency mirroring living systems ability to be self-sustaining. 		TRL@M0: 3
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● FMDC will be extended to follow edge-as-a-service principles with autonomy at the edge and federation across the fog and cloud. ● Provides the implementation of a hardware root of trust by utilising the existing features of its FMDCs. 		TRL@M36: 5
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: FMDC in the fog layer will be responsible for communication between cloud and edge layer. It will primarily respond to data flows and take action on the data based on their relevance and prioritisation in the edge layer. On top of that it will timely feed information and insights from the fog and cloud applications to the edge devices. The assessment at M18 will focus on: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Resource management at FMDC i.e. demonstration of the workload deployment inside FMDC using information exchange with MIRTO agent via common Interface. ● Monitoring and observability capabilities for FMDC using prometheus³. 		
Expected Results@M18: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Demonstration of successful WL placement at FMDC via MIRTO agent in the context of the UC scenarios. 		

- Demonstration of successful integration of the tools for Monitoring & Observability to measure FMDC's metrics (e.g. CPU, memory utilisation, etc.) and workload deployed at FMDC.

**According to the Grant Agreement this will not be distributed Open Source*

4.1.1.5 R5 – Cloud federated functions for compatibility with the Gaia-X trust model

Identifier: R5		Partner: TNO
Name: Cloud federation functions compatible with Gaia-X trust model.		
Licence: N.A.*	Owner: TNO	Contacts: joost.adriaanse@tno.nl bart.driessen@tno.nl julio.deoliveirafilho@tno.nl
Short Description: The Gaia-X Trust Framework allows providers to securely share and federate services between their infrastructures. It will be ensured MIRTO functions/services are compatible with the Gaia-X trust model.		
Baseline: The baseline is the definition of the Gaia-x trust framework ⁴ .		TRL@M0: 4
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. MIRTO agents will follow Gaia-X Trust Framework recommendations to trust other MIRTO agents and secure the communication between MIRTO agents. 2. Generate guidelines for developing MYRTUS-compliant applications that are in line with the Gaia-X Trust Framework. <p>Key aspects of compliance will relate to:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Data Protection and Security:</i> Ensuring that data is protected and secure, meeting high standards for privacy and data handling. • <i>Transparency:</i> Providing clear and accessible information about services and data usage. • <i>Interoperability:</i> Ensuring that different systems and services can work together seamlessly. • <i>Sovereignty and Control:</i> Giving users control over their data and ensuring that data sovereignty is respected. • <i>Trust Anchors:</i> Using trusted entities to validate and sign claims, ensuring the authenticity and integrity of data. 		TRL@M36: 6
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: Inspection if trust levels are defined for different services and functions of MIRTO.		
Expected Results@M18: Definition of the trust levels and identification of complacency rules applicable for different services and functions of the MIRTO orchestration tool.		

**Being basically an offered functionality, it will be implemented within MIRTO agents.*

4.1.2 Reachability of the Planned Operational Objective

At the time being all the planned operational objectives (OO) are still considered reachable throughout the planned results. The tables below discuss in more details with respect to the

⁴ <https://gaia-x.eu/>

Grant Agreement how the individual results are expected to contribute to the planned OOs. Please note that with respect to T1.OO.c “Ensure compatibility with the Gaia-X Trust Framework for MYRTUS nodes”, R3 (ABI gateway) and R4 (HIRO FMDC) being at the cloud-fog interface are currently under consideration for implementing such a support.⁵

T1.OO.a - Provide a layered reference infrastructure representing the skeleton of MYRTUS compliant systems, capable of ubiquitous data acquisition and distributed intelligent decision-making.

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R1	HMPSoCs FPGA-based CGR accelerators offer advanced close-to-source edge processing capabilities and, exploiting the onboard heterogeneity, will be able to run MIRTO agents feeding them with the needed execution information to make proper and effective decisions.
R2	The integrated processor + CGRA systems will be one of the available node-level flavours in the MYRTUS reference infrastructure at the edge and will feature internal and external monitoring capabilities together with on-board run-time management mechanisms that are MIRTO-compatible.
R3	The multi-sensor gateway is generic and modular and can therefore be used as the basis for defining a generic template for this kind of devices at the fog layer.
R4	FMDC will act as an intermediate component in the fog layer for interaction between edge and cloud communication and handles workload management. It already supports internal intelligence and will be able to run the MIRTO cognitive engine to provide both horizontal and vertical WLS orchestration.
R5	The developed layered reference architecture will make use of cloud federation functionality to ensure loads can be shared and shifted between different cloud providers.

T1.OO.b - Provide customizable, adaptive and efficient fog/edge nodes: including adaptable computing devices, small, energy efficient micro datacentres, and modular gateway, to bridge edge and far cloud.

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R1	HMPSoCs FPGA-based CGR accelerators can be customised to different computing problems; therefore, can be used as customizable computing nodes in MYRTUS-compliant computing infrastructures.
R2	The integrated processor + CGRA systems will offer an adaptive computing fabric to automatically offload generic software sections (e.g., massive loops) onto dedicated hardware resources that can be easily modified at runtime.
R3	The multi-sensor gateway is modular, and its interfaces are extensible and customizable.
R4	FMDC is a modular, composable Fog datacentre, compact and energy efficient with built-in intelligence to manage the workloads across distributed infrastructure of the fog.

⁵<https://prometheus.io/>

T1.00.c - Ensure compatibility with the Gaia-X Trust Framework for MYRTUS nodes (following the guidelines defined by the Gaia-X digital clearing house).

Mapped Result	Contribution
R3	<i>[Not originally planned in the Grant Agreement]</i> , Technical discussions are ongoing, to understand the technical needs and the cost for extending the gateway to support the Trust Framework at the fog-cloud interface.
R4	<i>[Not originally planned in the Grant Agreement]</i> Technical discussions are ongoing, to understand the technical needs and the cost for enabling FMDC hardware root of trust to support Gaia-X Trust Framework.
R5	MIRTO agents will follow Gaia-X Trust Framework recommendations and guidelines for developing MYRTUS-compliant applications (in line with the Gaia-X Trust Framework) will be distributed.

4.1.3 KPIs and M18 Assessment Plan

In the Grant Agreement we specified the KPIs to be achieved throughout Pillar 1 technologies, which are not changed. The tables below discuss how the identified results contribute to demonstrating those KPIs.

KPI1.1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure will be capable of integrating at least 2 cloud regions and 3/4 edge/fog environments composed of heterogeneous devices (e.g., CPU, GPU, FPGA, etc.), guaranteeing 100% availability of services for edge devices and near real time interactivity (<5ms) leveraging on the fog.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R1	Provide 1 edge component integrating heterogeneous FPGA-based edge nodes, while also providing the required software services to support the integration within the cloud-edge continuum (e.g., hardware virtualization, orchestration via Kubernetes).
R2	Provide 1 edge-to-fog component using reconfigurable FPGA devices as the substrate to implement full adaptive RISC-V, while also providing the required software services to support the integration within the cloud-edge continuum (e.g., hardware virtualization, orchestration via Kubernetes).
R3	Provide a multi-sensor gateway, at fog layer, connected with at least the R1 node at the edge.
R4	FMDC will implement Gaia-x compliant cloud federated functionality that stretches across cloud and edge layer and will be connected with heterogeneous devices at the edge and cloud.
R5	As the MYRTUS reference architecture will make use of Gaia-x compliant cloud federation functionalities, it will be possible to securely and trustworthy share and shift WLS between providers of cloud, fog, and edge devices.

KPI1.2 - One order of magnitude performance improvement using dedicated accelerators at the edge/fog layer.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R1	Demonstrate latency execution reduction with regards to reference software implementations running on the same node/platform/device, thanks to edge acceleration capabilities.

R2	Dedicated hardware accelerators will guarantee measurable performance improvements with regards to reference software implementations running on the same node/platform/device.
R3	The multi-sensor gateway, at the fog layer, will connect the heterogeneous edge components and enable efficient and seamless edge-to-fog exchanges (and vice versa).
R4	Energy saving and timely communication of insight- information will be enabled on high WLS by using the FMDC, which will also connect to heterogeneous edge components (CPUs/GPUs/FPGAs-based) and enable efficient and seamless edge-to-fog exchanges (and vice versa). FMDC will provide medium- to long-term data to extend the capabilities of the devices at the edge with additional analytics services.

KPI1.3 - 10-20% better energy efficiency when using heterogeneous HW/SW edge/fog computing solutions.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R1	Demonstrate energy efficiency with regards to reference software implementations running on the same node/platform/device, thanks to the reconfiguration and/or computing approximation capabilities supported within the HMPSoC FPGA-based accelerators.
R2	Dedicated hardware accelerators will provide measurable energy efficiency improvements with regards to reference software implementations running on the same node/platform/device
R4	Offloading the WLS from edge devices to the FMDC fog to provide 10-20% energy efficiency.

4.2 Pillar 2

Pillar 2 in a Nutshell

Technical Challenge: Cloud, fog and edge-devices are currently handled as different isolated silos, preventing an application to be seamlessly deployed and dynamically updated for continuous optimization, strategic to foster a sustainable computing approach, across continuum.

Technical Objective: MYRTUS features a 360° dynamic runtime orchestration scheme, embodied within the MIRTO AI-powered cognitive engine, to guarantee high performance and energy efficiency, preserving security and trust.

Key Enabling Technology: This pillar develops MIRTO: a multi-layer, distributed, and cognitive orchestration engine able to solve the resource allocation problem at a scalable, dynamic, and highly distributed heterogeneous infrastructure. MIRTO embraces an autonomic computing paradigm, which exploits self-awareness to implement self-reconfiguration, through feedback control loops and self-healing/-optimization capabilities.

The high-level overview of the **MIRTO cognitive engine**, depicted in Figure 4-3, still maintains the main elements discussed in the Grant Agreement, and emphasises the four aspects that should be in place for the orchestration task: (1) *sensing* of internal and external triggers for the orchestration; (2) *evaluation* of aggregated local and global information; (3) *decision* for resource allocations to improve KPIs and based on historical data; and (4) *reconfiguration* strategies per layer and in target dependent manner.

The first months of work in WP5 started with:

1. refining the internal architecture of the MIRTO cognitive engine, see below discussion of this initial version;
2. describing the information flow and operation process within the MIRTO engine; and
3. positioning initial interfaces to the users of the MIRTO agent (agent API) and to the infrastructure elements -- knowledge base, monitors, and low-level orchestration controllers -- which are provided in Pillar 1.

Please note that in this refined MIRTO architecture two original modules are not there: the *WL analysis and characterization* and the *Continuum Lifecycle Controller*. The former is meant to provide information to MIRTO agents, while the latter (based on LIQO) is meant to allow clustering and resource virtualization being somehow the interface between low level Kubernetes-based orchestration provided by the MYRTUS infrastructure elements, and MIRTO agents that are intended to perform the high-level orchestration.

The next step will be on identifying and specifying the interfaces to (1) resource monitors and registries, (2) knowledge base, and (3) deployment engine. MYRTUS intends to specify these interfaces independent of the infrastructure technology used -- for example, the knowledge base interface should not create a dependency to any database technology. Nevertheless, for purposes of implementation and demonstration of the project, the *implementation* of such interfaces in the project will be according to selected technologies.

Figure 4-3 - Multi-layer 360° dynamic RunTime Orchestration (MIRTO) cognitive engine [Grant Agreement, Part B page 9]

These activities put in place an initial architecture for the MIRTO engine, summarised in Figure 4-4. The MIRTO architecture is yet considered under development, not fully settled, and under continuous refinement between partners and other parts of the project. This initial architecture proposal:

- Creates a *MIRTO daemon API* defining the MIRTO agent as a (web-)service with a specification for its API. This REST-like API establishes how users will request orchestration activities to the MIRTO agent using TOSCA-based descriptions. It also puts in place a security *module for user authentication* and *TOSCA description validation*.
- Unifies the 4 management aspects mentioned in the Grant Agreement -- workload, node, network, and security/privacy -- into one sub-component, the *MIRTO Manager*, which is responsible to evaluate and decide on the allocation of resources managed by the agent and/or the configuration of the specific target (e.g. in the HMPSoC accelerators) to be executed. That is, all these aspects are still in place, and they will be considered together during the decision process since they might influence each other. The MIRTO manager is a cognitive component for which the MYRTUS project will develop several approaches (such as swarm-intelligence, distributed algorithms, and federated learning). This element of the MIRTO cognitive engine is the one explicitly mapping the EU-CEI building block related to Artificial Intelligence.

- Proposes *interface points (proxies)* to the infrastructure, knowledge base, and deployment (lifecycle) mechanisms that are developed in Pillar 1. These interfaces are also depicted earlier in Figure 4-2 (Pillar 1). The concrete specification and refinement of these interfaces is on-going work as specified at the beginning of Section 4.

Figure 4-4 – Main composing block of the current internal architecture of the MIRTO agent. MIRTO managers will come in different instances (depending on platform, layer, and cognitive approach). The interface envisions these managers will be interchangeable, whereas proxies, interfaces, and TOSCA processing modules will be common to different MIRTO agents.

Within this initial architectural design, we defined the flows of operations for basic operations, such as the request for deployment of a system. An example for the flow of information and processing within MIRTO can be seen in Figure 4-5.

The architecture of the MIRTO cognitive engine addresses many of the building blocks of the EU-CEI reference architecture. Specifically, MYRTUS will offer layer-specific MIRTO agents:

- Able to evaluate and decide on resource orchestration based on requirements for **security, trust & reputation**, and **data management standards** at all layers. The TOSCA description language here offers sufficient mechanisms to describe application requirements for these aspects. For example, a deployment request may indicate that some of the SW containers should only run within a certain security level and on a cluster trusted according to some standard. Also, requirements can be placed over the storage of data, e.g. that they should happen in an encrypted manner. Such requirements are part of the constraints to be solved by the MIRTO managers when allocating and optimising resources.
- Resource management, orchestration, and AI** aspects are combined in the MIRTO agent by the managers and according to the specific needs of each layer. At edge devices, MIRTO agents will use Machine Learning (ML)-based models to estimate the best operating point of a particular workload and reconfigure CGRA-based accelerators accordingly. Learned strategies from different MIRTO agents at the edge can be combined using federated learning techniques, allowing MIRTO agents to learn from each other's experiences without exchanging privacy details of their users. At the fog level, the MIRTO agent will monitor system data, and learn from previous events and interactions making informed decisions to maintain optimal system condition. MIRTO agents running on FMDC will manage the resources for optimal performance, resilience and efficiency. At cloud (and fog) level, different variants of MIRTO agents will be developed using orchestration decision strategies based on swarm-like intelligence, federated learning, and distributed optimization. At all levels, MIRTO agents communicate with each other to negotiate usage

of resources and interoperability of services over multiple layers. This aims at a seamless exchange of resources. MIRTO agents may operate under different AI-based algorithms reflecting the orchestration challenges and problems of the different layers. For example, MIRTO agents for dedicated accelerators may have a different level of granularity when deploying parts of an application.

Figure 4-5- Process flow within the MIRTO agent for a deployment request initiated with a TOSCA system description.

4.2.1 Expected Results

In this section all the expected Pillar 2 results are refined with respect to the Grant Agreement description. Please note that, as reported in Section 4.3, SAM tool which was originally planned to be used as an optimizer at design time, will be used instead by MIRTO cognitive engine at the manager level. Therefore, the associated R17 has been moved here, keeping the original numbering to avoid any confusion with other results.

4.2.1.1 R6 – AI models for WL characterization

Identifier: R6		Partner: UNISS UNICA UPM
Name: Models (AI and statistical) for WL characterization on edge technologies		
Licence: Apache Licence v2.0	Owner: UPM UNICA	UNISS Contacts: joseandres.otero@upm.es alfonso.rodriguez@upm.es francesca.palumbo@unica.it francesco.ratto@unica.it claudio.rubattu@uniss.it mfadda1@uniss.it prui@uniss.it

<p>Short Description: Approaches and methods for the characterization of the WLS, which encompass different techniques such as traditional statistical methods and ML-based models. These approaches will enable accurate both deployment-time and run-time estimations of different KPIs (e.g., execution latency/throughput, power/energy consumption). When possible, these models will support lifelong incremental learning to keep models up to date and consider unforeseen workload scenarios.</p>	
<p>Baseline: Several lightweight AI-based models are present at the state of the art, and among which those provided by UPM [ERO24].</p>	<p>TRL@M0: 2-3</p>
<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: Definition of methods for the characterization of a subset of possible WL which can be executed on the computing continuum. These methods will take in consideration the different HWs, the variety of WLS, the orchestration criteria and will produce a characterization based on statistical measures of the specific WL. For the WL FPGA-based acceleration, will be studied proper AI models depending on the chosen implementation strategy, which can follow i) the dataflow-oriented approach provided by UNISS and UNICA, ii) the strategy based on the adaptive RISC-V provided by UPM, or iii) a high-level synthesis flow of a commercial tool (e.g., Vitis AI). WLS will be characterised in terms of energy consumption, timing performance and processing accuracy. The defined models will be used by MIRTO within the node manager (R11).</p>	<p>TRL@M36: 4</p>
<p>Plans and Expectation</p>	
<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Evaluation/assessment of the WL characterization methods will be conducted using state-of-the-art datasets or by simulating data. Models for HMPSoCs will be assessed in the scenarios described in R1. Model accuracy will be assessed w.r.t. the actual metric values (e.g., processing latency, throughput, and power measurements). The models for the RISC-V processor with custom CGRA-based extensions will be assessed in the scenarios described in R2, evaluating deviations between model predictions and actual system measurements using dedicated circuitry/infrastructure.</p>	
<p>Expected Results@M18: Preliminary release of methods for the characterization of a subset of WLS which can be executed on the computing continuum. AI-based models with 90+% accuracy.</p>	

4.2.1.2 R7 – Chatbot WL implementation

<p>Identifier: R7 Partner: UNISS</p>		
<p>Name: Chatbot WL implementation</p>		
<p>Licence: Apache Licence v2.0</p>	<p>Owner: UNISS</p>	<p>Contacts: mfadda1@uniss.it pruiu@uniss.it</p>
<p>Short Description: Models based on LLM (Large Language Models) will be released, capable of receiving a specific workload as input (e.g., application, Docker, raw code) and producing an optimized version according to specific criteria (e.g., latency, security, energy consumption). The production of these models will begin with pre-trained models, utilising transfer learning techniques. The models will be specialized for the specific task through various fine-tuning techniques.</p>		
<p>Baseline: State of the art AI model for code generation (CodeBERT [FGT20], Code LLAMA⁶, Mistral [JSM23] , Code Gemma [TMH24]).</p>		<p>TRL@M0: 2</p>

⁶ <https://ai.meta.com/research/publications/code-llama-open-foundation-models-for-code/>.

MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: AI model fine tuned to generate code optimised according to the specific criteria of MIRTO cognitive engine (e.g. energy consumption, security, performance, throughput, etc.)	TRL@M36: 3-4
Plans and Expectation	
Assessment Plan@M18: N/A at M18 since this activity will start in the second project iteration.	
Expected Results@M18: N/A at M18 since this activity will start in the second project iteration.	

4.2.1.3 R8 – Swarm-based orchestration algorithms

Identifier: R8		Partner: LAKE HIRO
Name: Swarm-based orchestration algorithms		
Licence: Apache Licence v2.0	Owner: LAKE HIRO	Contacts: schranz@lakeside-labs.com wu@lakeside-labs.com fred.buining@hiro-microdatacenters.nl Veena.Rao@hiro-microdatacenters.nl Rahul.Sharma@hiro-microdatacenters.nl sai.kireeti@hiro-microdatacenters.nl
Short Description: Library of swarm-based orchestration algorithms based on natural inspiration and evolutionary computation for dynamic 360° scheduling (horizontal and vertical) at edge-fog-cloud layer.		
Baseline: Starting from LAKE experience in modelling agents for swarm-based orchestration from another EU-Horizon project (ACES ⁷), synergies to the edge continuum are there. In MYRTUS we will expand the behaviour of the swarm to the fog and cloud. This will directly influence agent-based modelling.		TRL@M0: 3
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: The novelty lies in the consideration of the 360° perspective of the MYRTUS project. LAKE's innovative contribution relates to the swarm intelligence component that will work on the emergent distribution of pods among the edge-fog-cloud continuum.		TRL@M36: 4-5
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: The baseline algorithms will be random workload placement and/or round robin. Assessment at cloud and fog (e.g. on the FMDC) are envisioned. Metrics: Satisfaction of processed pods and resource utilisation.		
Expected Results@M18:		
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Agent-based modelling of the edge-fog-cloud continuum. • Simulation framework to test a first swarm intelligence approach. • (Intermediate) implementation of ant/hormone-inspired swarm algorithm to find the best place for the pod to be processed compared to a baseline. 		

4.2.1.4 R9 – Library of Multi-agent RL algorithms and hierarchical and asynchronous FL algorithms across cloud, fog, and edge

Identifier: R9	Partner: KCL HIRO
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⁷ <https://www.aces-edge.eu/>

Name: Library of Multi-agent RL algorithms and hierarchical and asynchronous FL algorithms across cloud, fog, and edge		
Licence: TBD*	Owner: KCL HIRO	Contacts: yansha.deng@kcl.ac.uk na.2.yan@kcl.ac.uk fred.buining@hiro-microdatacenters.nl Veena.Rao@hiro-microdatacenters.nl Rahul.Sharma@hiro-microdatacenters.nl sai.kireeti@hiro-microdatacenters.nl
Short Description: Develop a cluster-based asynchronous FL framework which can be implemented into cloud/fog/edge networks.		
Baseline: State-of-the-art works related to multi-tiered and clustered asynchronous Federated Learning (FL) [ZDS22,XKG19].		TRL@M0: 2
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: KCL will provide a tier-based asynchronous FL framework capable of mitigating staleness and model bias resulting from system and data heterogeneity. While HIRO will provide model management support and model serving framework.		TRL@M36: 3-4
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: The performance of the proposed schemes will be evaluated through simulations developed using PyTorch. The focus will be on assessing learning accuracy/latency/communication overhead by training convolutional neural networks (CNNs) on the MNIST dataset. To carry out the assessment of the proposed strategies HIRO will provide a library compatible with the FMDC AI engine to generate/train models in the pipeline from the FL algorithms provided by KCL.		
Expected Results@M18: 8% improvement in training efficiency of FL and the model accuracy of asynchronous FL.		

*Current TRL level is still too low, and technical discussions are ongoing. Therefore, licensing decisions have been postponed to the second project iteration.

4.2.1.5 R10 – Service chains

Identifier: R10		Partner: TNO
Name: Dynamic service chains composition		
Licence: Apache License v2.0 - as part of a MIRTO manager functionality	Owner: TNO	Contacts: julio.deoliveirafilho@tno.nl bart.driessen@tno.nl coen.vanleeuwen@tno.nl
Short Description: Dynamic functional composition of service chains allows a MIRTO agent to instantiate different service chains configurations depending on the actual conditions and resource availability. The MIRTO agent will be able, for example, to dynamically decide and exchange between different service implementations -- given the implementations satisfy the requirements of other (user) services		
Baseline: TNO has several algorithms developed for design exploration and assessment of service chains at runtime. These algorithms can be combined with optimization techniques, such as the ones available in SAM (see R17).		TRL@M0: 3
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: One of the instances for the MIRTO cognitive engine, namely the one using distributed optimization techniques based on SAM, will enable dynamical composition of service		TRL@M36: 5

chains that define how applications will be deployed on specific infrastructures.	
Plans and Expectation	
<p>Assessment Plan@M18: The results will be assessed in the smart mobility assessment scenario. It will be assessed by artificially creating the need for different service chain solutions, e.g. by emulating changes in traffic density. Such changes in the conditions of the system will deploy solution solely defined at runtime (in contrast to just switching between pre-defined solutions).</p>	
<p>Expected Results@M18: MIRTO agents -- at least the MIRTO manager based on SAM -- will be able to create dynamic allocations for the system deployment depending on actual resource usage and KPI goals. At this phase, the dynamic allocation is still limited to within the resource pool of an agent.</p>	

4.2.1.6 R11 – OS-based manager for FPGA based edge devices

Identifier: R11		Partner: UNISS UNICA UPM	
Name: <i>OS-based manager for FPGA based edge devices</i>			
Licence: Apache Licence v2.0	Owner: UNISS UNICA UPM ABI	Contacts: claudio.rubattu@uniss.it francesca.palumbo@unica.it francesco.ratto@unica.it joseandres.otero@upm.es alfonso.rodruiguez@upm.es tiziana.fanni@abinsula.com	
<p>Short Description: OS-based and MIRTO-compatible manager to enable workload orchestration with standard interfaces (e.g., Kubernetes) but also providing low-level and node-specific resource management mechanisms to adapt the working point at run time (i.e., changing the configuration of the HMPSoCs or the RISC-V processor with custom CGRA-based extensions, which require different tuning knobs).</p>			
<p>Baseline: State-of-the-art works related to the runtime management of application features [DCK22, GGT23]. In addition, since AI models (R6.a) require application data exchange from Edge to Cloud to enable model updating and WL orchestration, this can be managed by an operating system such as the customizable Yocto-based Embedded Linux Distribution (Ability) provided by ABI.</p>			TRL@M0: 2
<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: Implementation of a node manager to be integrated within the MIRTO cognitive engine to ensure the seamless usage of the edge components in the continuum.</p>			TRL@M36: 4-5
Plans and Expectation			
<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Node manager for HMPSoCs will be assessed in the scenarios described in R1. The node manager for the RISC-V processor with custom CGRA-based extensions will be assessed in the scenarios described in R2.</p>			
<p>Expected Results@M18: Availability of at least two node manager implementations capable of making possible the orchestration of edge-based FPGA nodes in the continuum, where the low-level hardware management is node-specific but the high-level interface with the continuum is common, standard and unified among them.</p>			

4.2.1.7 R12 – AI-enabled network manager

Identifier: R12	Partner: KCL HIRO
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Name: Network manager		
Licence: TBD*	Owner: KCL HIRO	Contacts: yansha.deng@kcl.ac.uk na.2.yan@kcl.ac.uk fred.buining@hiro-microdatacenters.nl Veena.Rao@hiro-microdatacenters.nl Rahul.Sharma@hiro-microdatacenters.nl sai.kireeti@hiro-microdatacenters.nl
Short Description: AI-enabled network manager for network resource orchestration.		
Baseline: State-of-the-art related to cloud-fog-edge network management [KYL23], such as resource allocation and task scheduling, to manage the energy consumption or the latency.	TRL@M0: 2	
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: AI models will be used to make real-time decisions on whether to process tasks locally on edge devices, at fog nodes, or in the cloud with the aim to improve the latency or the energy consumption.	TRL@M36: 3-4	
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: The learning algorithm will utilise reinforcement learning. The performance of the proposed scheme will be evaluated by comparing its performance against conventional non-AI methods.		
Expected Results@M18: The expected latency improvement is 5%.		

*Current TRL level is still too low, and technical discussions are ongoing. Therefore, licensing decisions have been postponed to the second project iteration.

4.2.1.8 R13 – Models of selected homomorphic encryption, multi-party computation, and FL open-source libraries suitable for continuous monitoring.

Identifier: R13		Partner: USI
Name: Models of selected security and privacy primitives suitable for continuous monitoring.		
Licence: TBD, likely Apache Licence v2.0	Owner: USI	Contacts: francesco.regazzoni@usi.ch tom.slooff@usi.ch subhadeep.banik@usi.ch
Short Description: USI will generate models concerning several computational metrics of selected security and privacy primitives, such as symmetric encryption, authenticated encryption, homomorphic encryption, multi-party computation, and federated learning. The models will be based on open-source libraries suitable for continuous monitoring.		
Baseline: There are existing implementations of security and privacy primitives, for example symmetric encryption (e.g. OpenSSL ⁸), authenticated encryption (e.g. ASCON ⁹), homomorphic encryption (e.g. OpenFHE ¹⁰ , SEAL ¹¹), multi-party computation (e.g. MP-SPDZ ¹²), and federated learning (e.g. PySyft ¹³ , Flower ¹⁴). However, none of these		TRL@M0: 2

⁸ <https://github.com/openssl/openssl>

⁹ <https://github.com/ascon/ascon-c>

¹⁰ <https://www.openfhe.org/>

¹¹ <https://github.com/microsoft/SEAL>

¹² <https://github.com/data61/MP-SPDZ>

¹³ <https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft>

¹⁴ <https://github.com/adap/flower>

implementations have been modelled in a way that can be used in MYRTUS. Nonetheless, even if this can not be considered the baseline, the existing implementations provide a good starting point for the modelling.	
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: Models of computational metrics of selected libraries that have been identified as suitable for continuous monitoring, based on benchmarks performed on the selected libraries.	TRL@M36: 4
Plans and Expectation	
Assessment Plan@M18: The generated models at this point will be evaluated on their accuracy. The models are based on benchmarks performed throughout the project. To evaluate the model, we will use it to predict the computational requirements on a new platform and evaluate its accuracy.	
Expected Results@M18: At least one library should be modelled and evaluated. The accuracy of the model should be high enough to use the model reliably for the orchestration task.	

4.2.1.9 R14 – Virtual continuum library

Identifier: R14		Partner: ARK
Name: Virtual continuum library		
Licence: Apache Licence v2.0	Owner: ARK	Contacts: luca.castello@arubakube.cloud giuseppe.zangari@arubakube.cloud francesco.cheinasso@arubakube.cloud
Short Description: Library and tools to create a dynamic, virtual continuum on top of a fragmented cloud-edge infrastructure.		
Baseline: The project leverages LIQO ¹⁵ to establish a seamless cloud continuum across various cloud environments. Liqo is instrumental in enabling the integration and interoperable management of resources between distinct cloud platforms.	TRL@M0: 2	
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: MIRTUS novelty is the evolution of algorithms that will enable the cloud continuum between the cloud and edge resources. Addressing also additional requirements such as: network constraints, bandwidth, latency and reliability.	TRL@M36: 4-5	
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: Evaluation of interoperability, latency, bandwidth, resource utilisation, reliability, and security between resources in the cloud and on the edge. This implies enabling the continuum within the assessment scenario's cloud-edge infrastructure to schedule/move WLS on both MYRTUS assessment scenarios. More concretely, at M18 we envision to be able to successfully establish the continuum between at least one MYRTUS edge node and one cloud cluster.		
Expected Results@M18: Availability of cloud continuum between simulated cloud/fog and edge.		

4.2.1.10 R17 – SAM

Identifier: R17		Partner: TNO
Name: SAM		
Licence: Apache License v2.0	Owner: TNO	Contacts: coen.vanleeuwen@tno.nl

¹⁵ <https://www.arubakube.cloud/#liqo>

<p>Short Description: SAM is a toolbox for solving Distributed Constraint Optimization Problems (DCOP), in MYRTUS this will be used by modelling the job/node resource allocation problem as a DCOP, using the outcome of DynAA (which is explained as part of Pillar 3, but it will be used at runtime too), allowing to use its algorithms at design-time and at runtime.</p>	
<p>Baseline: SAM is an existing toolbox for solving DCOPs, and has been applied in several domains, e.g. for energy, transport and sensor networks. An implementation exists in Java, based on which several papers have been published and proven stable [LP17, POL22]. A new version written in python is in beta, which offers a higher ease of use and integration with DynAA.</p>	<p>TRL@M0: 2-3</p>
<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: SAM will be used as one of the (distributed) reasoning mechanisms to solve the resource allocation problem at runtime, that maps software components (tasks or services as pods or containers) to the digital infrastructure of MYRTUS. The optimization criterion for the resource allocation problem is a set of hard constraints, plus a cost function provided to SAM. This metric is still to be defined but could be a user requirement such as the response time, or latency, or something else such as the total energy usage, or the number of processors needed based on the simulation output. A combination of factors is very likely, but then some kind of aggregation function needs to be defined as well.</p>	<p>TRL@M36: 3-4</p>
<p>Plans and Expectation</p>	
<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Initial implementation of the optimization loop in the MIRTO agent using SAM and a (simple) cost function definition, should demonstrate the functionality. Integration with the DynAA simulation framework is optional in M18 but will be further implemented.</p>	
<p>Expected Results@M18: Integration of SAM in the MIRTO agent, as one of the variants of a cognitive engine (manager).</p>	

4.2.2 Reachability of the Planned Operational Objective

At the time being all the planned operational objectives (OO) are still considered reachable throughout the planned results. The tables below discuss in more details with respect to the Grant Agreement how the individual results are expected to contribute to the planned OOs. Please note that R17, moved from Pillar 3 to Pillar 2, has been added to the tables below.

<p>T2.OO.a - Formalization of a generic multi-layer cognitive self-adaptation engine constituted of different resource- and layer- specific agents, implementing customised management.</p>	
<p>Mapped Result</p>	<p>Contribution</p>
<p>R6</p>	<p>Workload characterization based on lifelong/incremental ML models to estimate relevant KPIs (e.g., latency/throughput, power/energy).</p>
<p>R7</p>	<p>Optimization of WL at deployment time through an LLM-based approach</p>
<p>R8</p>	<p>Agent-based modelling of the system to create an adaptive and robust decentralised system that can cope with the dynamics of the individual agents' availability, resource capability and agents' tasks</p>
<p>R9</p>	<p>The cluster-based asynchronous federated learning framework will be able to dynamically cluster the users and configure the training process to deal with the system heterogeneity including the various capabilities of the edge</p>

	devices in MIRTO to improve the training efficiency.
R10, R17	Dynamic service chain composition will support self-adaptation at the service level by computing optimal reallocation, leveraging SAM solver.
R11	The node manager for FPGA-based heterogeneous nodes (R1 and R2) to be used in MIRTO cognitive engine will specifically address self-adaptation on edge nodes.
R12	The network manager will include an AI-based strategy for optimising the resource and network management of MIRTO.
R13	The privacy and security manager will include a model of generic privacy preserving libraries to be used in MIRTO cognitive engine agents regardless of the considered layer/component.
R14	Virtualization techniques, already available in the farther layer of the continuum, are meant to be ported to edge nodes, such as specific FPGA-based heterogeneous nodes.

T2.OO.b - Definition of novel AI-powered management strategies and libraries of orchestration algorithms, based on SI and FL methodologies, to provide 360° orchestration of resources/tasks/services/security aspects.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R8	Swarm intelligence approaches will be used for the emergent workload placement to achieve both horizontal and vertical WL distribution.
R9	Advanced resource allocation algorithms for hierarchical FL systems will be adopted within the MIRTO cognitive engine to improve the communication efficiency of the FL process.
R10	The dynamic functional composition of service chains will leverage AI-powered strategies (such as distributed agent-based optimization -- see also R17) and help the creation of libraries of orchestration algorithms.
R11	The AI models used within the node manager are expected to continuously evolve at runtime, and FL strategies will be adopted to (exploiting proper support at the fog layer) achieve consensus and model redistribution.
R12	Advanced AI-powered strategies will be adopted within the MIRTO cognitive engine to improve the latency or the consumption of the MIRTO system.
R13	With the use of appropriate functional and non-functional models, the engine can orchestrate the security dimension in the continuum.
R17	One of the MIRTO agents' variants will leverage SAM for solving the orchestration with distributed optimization techniques.

T2.OO.c – Definition of different AI models for WL characterization at deployment/runtime time.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R6, R11	WL characterization on application specific heterogeneous accelerators (R1 and R2) will favour the definition of models to be used (and possibly retrained using lifelong and/or incremental learning mechanisms, see

	T2.OO.b) at runtime to estimate KPIs and autonomously take runtime decisions. Indeed, the node manager of MIRTO cognitive engine on edge devices is expected to be able to decide, autonomously and based on models derived from workload characterization, about the workpoint activation of co-processing units.
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T2.OO.d - Definition of an AI-based optimization module capable of re-engineering part incoming WLS to make them more performing while running on the computing continuum.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R7	Models based on LLM (Large Language Models) capable of receiving a specific WLS as input and producing optimised versions according to specific criteria (e.g., latency, security, energy consumption). The production of these models will begin with pre-trained models, utilising transfer learning techniques. The optimised version of the WLS will be more performing while running on the computing continuum.
R10, R17	The orchestration problem to be solved using SAM will consider the possibility of using different service implementations to compose or select dynamically the system composition to be used. Different service chains will be considered and selected according to their performance indicators during runtime.

T2.OO.e - Support legacy systems leveraging on widely adopted technologies, such as TOSCA and Kubernetes.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R14	The envisioned cloud-fog-edge virtualization techniques will facilitate low-level orchestration of the continuum, supporting also Kubernetes integration with legacy systems when applicable.

4.2.3 KPIs and M18 Assessment Plan

In the Grant Agreement we specified the KPIs to be achieved throughout Pillar 2 technologies, which are not changed. The tables below discuss how the identified results contribute to demonstrating those KPIs.

KPI2.1 - MIRTO transfers processes amongst at least 3 different processing/instruction set architectures for edge/fog/cloud nodes and is deployed and used in at least 2 cloud-edge scenarios outside the consortium.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R9	Provide a cluster-based hierarchical federated learning framework and a training configuration scheme that is applicable to any cluster standard. This framework can be applied to cloud-fog-edge MIRTO scenarios and can be extended to any cloud-edge or fog-edge scenarios.
R10, R17	The MIRTO agent based on the distributed optimization strategies offered by SAM will be able to perform dynamically service chain composition between edge/fog/cloud nodes, if candidate nodes provide the necessary requirements (e.g. same interface).
R11	Provide 1 fog-edge heterogeneous environment composed of heterogeneous FPGA-based edge components mastered in the continuum

	using MIRTO agents. Explore the possibility of using additional components (not developed within MYRTUS) with alternative reconfiguration and acceleration capabilities but compatible cloud-edge continuum mechanisms to be used as reference for third-party FPGA-based component integration/deployment.
R12	Provide an ISA agnostic AI-based network management strategy that can be used for edge/fog/cloud resource management, which is also applicable to similar edge networks.
R13	At least one of the privacy-preserving functions will be implemented as a moving agent between different heterogeneous MYRTUS infrastructure components.
R14	LIQO virtualization technologies will allow supporting different Kubernetes-compliant processing nodes considering, at least, 3 different processing/instruction set architectures.

KPI2.2 - Provide at least 20% improvements in all the considered applications' KPIs (as throughput, energy efficiency, processing and communication latency, network availability, bandwidth etc.) using MIRTO AI-powered strategies. Comparisons (simulations and testbed implementations) with/without the proposed strategies.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R6	The definition of accurate AI models to optimise deployment and execution of workloads for FPGA-based edge nodes. Moreover, the possibility of making these models evolve using lifelong and/or incremental learning mechanisms will ensure that the best working point is selected for each workload in each node.
R7	The optimization of WL carried out according to specific criteria of MIRTO cognitive engine, will improve its performance, energy consumption, security, together with throughput, latency and other critical functional parameters.
R8	Due to the agent-based modelling, the MIRTO agents can make quick and local decisions that reduce the latency in taking action. New appearing agents in the system (on resource and demand level) use local information to (get) orchestrate(d) in the dynamic edge-fog-cloud continuum. This reduces latency and increases the throughput of the entire system.
R9	The proposed training configuration scheme will be able to improve the latency or reduce the training time of the federated learning process implemented in MIRTO.
R11	The node manager of MIRTO cognitive engine on edge devices is expected to be able to take self-optimization decisions on the workpoint activation of co-processing units. This capability directly positively affects the improvement KPIs metrics at runtime.
R12	The node manager of MIRTO cognitive engine is expected to tackle energy efficiency or reduced communication latency.
R13	The privacy and security manager provides a measure of trust which can be

	used at runtime. The incorporation of trust into the runtime orchestration will provide improvements on KPIs related to availability and throughput.
R14	The library and tools to create a dynamic virtual cloud-fog-edge continuum will allow exporting computational components metrics (e.g. throughput, energy consumption, bandwidth, etc.) to enable MIRTO cognitive engine to carry out global optimizations.

KPI2.3 - Model and support at least 10 privacy preserving functions within MIRTO cognitive engine and deal with at least 3 types of restrictions (e.g., legal, geographical, or security) coming from the Gaia-X Framework.

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R13	With respect to privacy and security management, among the functionalities modelled there will be at least 10 and targeting at least 3 types of restrictions.
R14	The library and tools to create a dynamic virtual cloud-fog-edge continuum will enable MIRTO cognitive engine to identify and choose the right execution environment to support privacy preserving functions.

4.3 Pillar 3

Pillar 3 in a Nutshell

Technical Challenge: The more a system is heterogeneous, complex, and adaptive, the more designers rely on partially integrated tool chains/methodologies tuned for specific aspects. There is no effective interoperability.

Technical Objective: MYRTUS DPE for continuum computing systems, features interoperable support for cross layer modelling, threat analysis, design space exploration, modelling, components synthesis, and code generation.

Key Enabling Technology: The DPE judiciously integrates tools and standard formats, from high-level application specification to low-level deployment tools for heterogeneous nodes with a strong focus on interfaces and interoperability, facilitating the MYRTUS solutions uptake at large scale.

The original plan for the DPE (Pillar 3) from the Grant Agreement is shown in Figure 4-6. As the figure shows, the DPE is decomposed into three steps, namely, 1) a step for high-level modelling, simulation and analysis, 2) a step for turning the model into a concrete implementation, and 3) a step on node-level optimization and deployment of key computational kernels of the application. Following discussions during the initial phase of the project, some aspects of the DPE have been simplified while others have been refined. This is captured by the updated DPE flow depicted in Figure 4-7. Major changes include:

- Step 1: The SAM component was removed since it became clear the DynAA discrete event simulator suffices to provide high-level KPIs to the evolutionary optimizer in FREVO. The SAM component, however, will still be used at runtime by workload orchestrators (as already discussed in Pillar 2). Further, we decided that a custom format will be used for the interfacing between DynAA and FREVO, instead of using TOSCA for this. FREVO then exports the local rules of the agents in form of comma-separated values (or alike) to Modelio.

- Step2: A major refinement of Step 2 consists in components that will be generated by Modelio. These components or partitions follow from a high-level model-based analysis, using applications that are written in some other language (C/C++ or Python). These components can be either generated from other Design Specific Language (DSL) and/or ML frameworks or can come from existing C/C++ implementations (i.e., “Existing SW components code base” in Figure 3.2). Modelio extracts parts of the applications that require acceleration (e.g., DSP kernels). These parts are then passed to further optimization in Step 3 as part of the Deployment Specification for guiding compilation, optimization, and integration of the accelerated components. The rest of the application is compiled with standard compilers, while making sure that it can interoperate with the accelerated portions. The component-level view of the application is fed to the MIRTO cognitive engine (defining the interface from the DPE to Pillar 2) in the form of .tosca/.csar files.
- Step 3: A clear need for the Lingua Franca programming language has not been identified in this phase of the project and was thus temporarily removed from the figure of the DPE. However, the underlying concepts of adaptive dataflow with timing semantics (i.e., the abstract reactor model of Lingua Franca) will remain important for the intermediate models within the compilation flow. Mocasin will integrate at the level of dataflow to support Design Space Exploration (DSE) of CGRA kernels. Step 3 main MLIR dialects have been defined. dfg-mlir and cgra-mlir will model applications as dataflows and generate CGRA configurations, respectively. Existing dialects/tools will be leveraged from the MLIR ecosystem for accepting inputs in different languages (i.e., torch-mlir and Polygeist¹⁶) and target FPGA (generating Verilog to feed MDC) and CPU (through the LLVM Intermediate Representation). The deployment specification will be passed from Modelio to dfg-mlir in toska format (i.e., yaml).

Figure 4-6 – Original MYRTUS design and programming environment [Grant Agreement, Part B page 12]

¹⁶ <https://github.com/llvm/torch-mlir> and <https://polygeist.llvm.org/>.

Figure 4-7 - Refined MYRTUS design and programming environment.

4.3.1 Expected Results

In this section all the expected Pillar 3 results are refined with respect to the Grant Agreement description.

4.3.1.1 R15 – Modelio

Identifier: R15		Partner: SOFT
Name: Modelio		
Licence: GPL-3.0 licence	Owner: SOFT	Contacts: alessandra.bagnato@docaposte.fr juan.cadavid@docaposte.fr amina.moussaoui@docaposte.fr laurent.goncalves@docaposte.fr
Short Description: Modelio is a UML modelling environment, with available extensions such as Camel Designer or Model-driven Code Generation, supporting a wide range of models and diagrams and providing services facilitating architecture modelling/analysis. It will be made compatible with TOSCA descriptions and extended to feature threat modelling and propose countermeasures from a standard library.		
Baseline: Modelio supports a diverse range of models and diagrams for modelling, offering a user-friendly interface for creating, editing, and analysing architectural designs. It also provides extensions for Cloud Modelling like Cloud Application Modelling and Execution Language (CAMEL) Designer and Model-driven Code Generation to enhance functionality and streamline development processes.		TRL@M0: 2 (for Cloud Modelling)
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: Modelio will facilitate modelling of both TOSCA templates and Attack Trees seamlessly within the platform. This advancement enables users to leverage Modelio for comprehensive cloud application design using TOSCA standards while concurrently integrating sophisticated analysis of security threats through Attack Trees, streamlining the modelling process and enhancing overall system robustness.		TRL@M36: 5-6
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: Integration testing with a validation plan consisting of a test suite, with test cases for code generation, attack tree threats and countermeasures development.		

Expected Results@M18: First candidate release of Modelio Tosca Designer and Attack Tree Designer and Countermeasures module, with associated documentation. 50% of Tosca specification elements. Initial validation plan will consist of 10 integration test cases.

4.3.1.2 R16 – DynAA

Identifier: R16		Partner: TNO	
Name: DynAA			
Licence: Apache 2.0	Owner: TNO	Contacts: julio.deoliveirafilho@tno.nl	
Short Description: DynAA is a highly efficient system simulation engine based on discrete event specifications. In MYRTUS it will be used by FREVO and will be made compatible with Tosca descriptions.			
Baseline: DynAA discrete event engine is fully developed in TNO from other projects and as such a mature and already existing SW module. The engine is written in C++, highly performant and memory efficient -- that is, it is written to have a minimal footprint for the simulation models (on memory and performance). DynAA offers a Python integration wrapper -- called pyDynAA that eases the integration with prototypes and simulations driven from Python.			TRL@M0: 5-6
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: DynAA will be extended with a library of models that translate to basic system descriptions, such as the ones found in Tosca. This library will facilitate (and partially automate) the simulation of system compositions. Interfaces with MIRTO managers such as the ones based on SAM and FREVO will be implemented with this library. Such simulations can be used by orchestrators and managers at the MIRTO engine.			TRL@M36: 5-6
Plans and Expectation			
Assessment Plan@M18: Initial simulations of system models using DynAA will be demonstrated. Possibly already in combination with the FREVO tool, which delivers the topology model to be simulated. Assessment made at laboratory.			
Expected Results@M18: Transformation of topology system descriptions into DynAA models (possibly not yet automated) and demonstration of system simulations using DynAA.			

4.3.1.3 R18 – FREVO

Identifier: R18		Partner: LAKE	
Name: FREVO			
Licence: Apache 2.0	Owner: LAKE	Contacts: schrantz@lakeside-labs.com	
Short Description: FREVO optimises the parameters for decision making according to a desired emergent system behaviour by evolutionary design to create the rules for agents in self-organising systems. Results are rules/parameters used in the MIRTO cognitive engine to design distributed ML placement/orchestration rules that will be automatically synthesised for the first time.			
Baseline: FREVO is a framework for evolutionary design and offers multiple options for candidate representations (incl. fuzzy rules, FSM or ANN) as well as optimization method parameter selections. In several papers and implementations, we were able to show the stability and the diverse			TRL@M0: 3

possibilities for the application of FREVO to generate rules (even for swarms) using genetic manipulations.	
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: In MYRTUS we use FREVO to design rules for the WL manager based on evolutionary algorithms. As FREVO needs a simulation tool for mutating, selecting, generating candidate solutions (computed by evolutionary algorithms), we need a new interface (to DynAA or to the simulation framework designed to evaluate the swarm-based orchestration) to simulate the MYRTUS 360° vision to generate precisely such rules in combination with genetic manipulation.	TRL@M36: 4-5
Plans and Expectation	
Assessment Plan@M18: We have already derived all the requirements for the FREVO interface and finished the interface implementation to DynAA/self-designed simulation framework. For the assessment, we have established a first simulation loop with FREVO to create swarm behaviour with evolution.	
Expected Results@M18: Implementation of one interface to FREVO and get first results in the design of swarm behaviour with this tooling loop.	

4.3.1.4 R19 – Mocasin

Identifier: R19		Partner: TUD	
Name: Mocasin			
Licence: ISC licence	Owner: TUD	Contacts: jeronimo.castrillon@tu-dresden.de	
Short Description: Mocasin enables high-level trace-driven simulation/optimization for parallel applications (modelled as directed graphs) on heterogeneous systems (modelled as graphs with cost annotations). Node level metrics (e.g., execution time, and energy consumption) are reported by the tool. Mocasin will be extended to model reactive behaviour. Its library of platform models will be extended to support MYRTUS components, and the simulator core will support runtime adaptivity.			
Baseline: Mocasin supports task graphs, Kahn process networks and static dataflow graphs as models of computation to represent applications. In all cases, traces are used to model execution. As for the platforms, Mocasin supports simple ARM big.LITTLE multi-cores (with thorough calibration and good result fidelity). There is no support for reactive models, for application adaptation, nor for distributed execution.			TRL@M0: 2-3
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: Mocasin for modelling specialised RISC-V platforms with CGRAs. Extend support on the platform side to include distributed nodes. Extend MOC support to reactive and/or adaptable application models.			TRL@M36: 3-4
Plans and Expectation			
Assessment Plan@M18: Mocasin should provide initial support for application adaptation (changing graph topology, changing mapping to react to environment). This will be measured with mock-application models, reporting performance and energy variations as a consequence of the adaptation. Initial support for the platforms developed in MYRTUS will be assessed by modelling simple CGRAs, calibrating to an error in latency of less than 20% for single kernels (tensor expression, signal processing kernels).			
Expected Results@M18: 3 out of the following 5 features supported: modelling changing topology, modelling time-triggered actions, modelling input from external sources for			

runtime adaptation, modelling CGRA and platform-side reconfiguration, calibrated models for simple kernels with error below 20%.

4.3.1.5 R20 – Lingua Franca

Identifier: R20		Partner: TUD
Name: Lingua Franca		
Licence: BSD 2-Clause	Owner: TUD (member of a larger international collaboration)	Contacts: jeronimo.castrillon@tu-dresden.de
<p>Short Description: Lingua Franca is a polyglot coordination programming language (supporting C/C++, Python, etc.) to represent programs based on the reactor programming model. Reactors describe distributed/concurrent applications with explicit semantics of time, allowing both compiler and runtime to reason about time-sensitive cyber physical systems' applications and providing guarantees with respect to determinism. New MLIR dialects for the reactor model will be developed along with novel support for mutations for adaptive execution.</p>		
<p>Baseline: Lingua Franca is a large project which supports reaction code written in C/C++, Python, and Rust (to some extent). It has initial support for federated execution on mainstream computing systems. Its compiler is based on xText that uses a language server protocol. Lingua Franca is based on the formal reactor model of computation. There is close to no support for mutations in the C/C++ target and no use cases use this feature.</p>		TRL@M0: 3
<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: A programming abstraction that supports adaptability and models reactive behaviour, based on the reactor model which underlies Lingua Franca. Independent of the syntax, we want to define proper intermediate dialects in MLIR to represent the application graphs and capture the semantics of the model of computation. At M8 we decided to make this independent of the syntax, since at the point of writing, it is unclear what the preferred language will be for critical parts of the use cases. This will allow interoperability with other higher-level programming abstractions within MLIR (stemming from Domain Specific Languages, DSL) and with downstream compilation flows. The programming abstraction supports distributed/federated execution.</p>		TRL@M36: 4-5
Plans and Expectation		
<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Basic MLIR dialects should capture the main semantics of the reactor model of computation needed to support application adaptivity and remapping in MYRTUS.</p>		
<p>Expected Results@M18: Simple reactive programs can be modelled in MLIR (w/o cycles in the reaction graph, single timer, logical actions), code can be generated and executed on a posix compliant platform.</p>		

4.3.1.6 R21 – MLIR-based Code-to-CGRA compiler infrastructure

Identifier: R21		Partner: UPM
Name: MLIR-based Code-to-CGRA compiler infrastructure		
Licence:	Owner: UPM	Contacts: joseandres.otero@upm.es

Apache Licence v2.0 with LLVM Exceptions		alfonso.rodruiguez@upm.es
<p>Short Description: Multigrain CGRA Overlay currently supports LLVM-based C-to-CGRA compilation with limited automatic parallelization capabilities. It will be reworked to have MLIR at its core, enabling code optimizations and deployment-oriented architectural modelling and simulation.</p>		
<p>Baseline: The first iteration of the Multigrain Reconfigurable CGRA overlay was developed as a custom memory-mapped accelerator to be loosely coupled with a processor core. To make it usable via user-friendly programming, an LLVM-based C-to-CGRA compilation framework was also developed. This compiler toolchain was able to take an input C code with manually tagged parallel sections and generate a) valid configuration bitstreams for the different PEs in the CGRA and b) the corresponding software code for the host processor to transparently offload computation to the CGRA. However, the toolchain lacked complex code optimizations to properly exploit the spatial parallelism of the computing fabric.</p>		TRL@M0: 2-3
<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: To provide an MLIR-based Code-to-CGRA compilation framework capable of a) automatically identifying the candidate functions/sections to be accelerated in HW, b) efficiently extracting parallelism at different levels using advanced optimization techniques such as polyhedral transformations, c) generating the associated binaries for both the processor and the CGRA under memory-mapped and extended-ISA scenarios and d) providing support for alternative entry points such as AI models (e.g., TensorFlow). To this end, at least one CGRA-specific MLIR dialect will be developed to properly support the IR-to-HW mapping process.</p>		TRL@M36: 4-5
<p>Plans and Expectation</p>		
<p>Assessment Plan@M18: Usage of the new MLIR-based Code-to-CGRA compilation framework to deploy manually identified code sections of application benchmarks (e.g., PolyBench) onto the CGRA fabric.</p>		
<p>Expected Results@M18: Proper application mapping onto the CGRA for the manually mapped code sections of all application benchmarks, and measurable performance improvements when compared against the reference software baseline running on the same host processor.</p>		

4.3.1.7 R22 – MDC

Identifier: R22		Partner: UNISS, UNICA	
Name: MDC			
Licence: 3-clause BSD		Owner: UNICA (with UNISS support in specific features)	Contacts: francesca.palumbo@unica.it francesco.ratto@unica.it claudio.rubattu@uniss.it
<p>Short Description: The Multi-Dataflow Composer (MDC) tool supports runtime adaptivity through the design and deployment of CGR accelerators.</p>			
<p>Baseline: MDC is an open-source design tool for the generation and management of Coarse-Grain Reconfigurable (CGR) Hardware Accelerators. The baseline tool supports multitasking through dataflow merging techniques. Input application must be specified in CAL language or ORCC IR</p>			TRL@M0: 3 (for what regards the features)

representation. High-level synthesis tools can be integrated as external tools provided that the developer specifies the modules' interface. A toolchain that takes as input a CNN in ONNX and includes MDC is partially integrated.	related to MYRTUS extensions)
<p>MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: MDC will be extended to support the design automation of multi-threaded accelerators exploiting tagged dataflow computation. The tool will also accept QONNX as input specification for the acceleration of Quantized CNN. Approximate computing will be supported through integration with Quantized NN (i.e. QONNX) and an HLS tool that supports fixed-point arithmetic (e.g. Vitis HLS). A new standalone version of the MDC tool will be made available by integrating these new features and removing dependencies from discontinued third-party components.</p>	TRL@M36: 4-5
Plans and Expectation	
Assessment Plan@M18: Usage of the new MDC features to create the accelerators listed in R1.	
Expected Results@M18: Partial availability of the new features to be integrated in the final version of MDC with accompanied distribution material (tutorial and GitHub code).	

4.3.1.8 R23 – DPE Step 3

Identifier: R23		Partner: TUD, ABI, UPM, UNICA
Name: DPE Step 3		
Licence: To be defined later ¹⁷	Owner: TUD, ABI, UPM, UNICA	Contacts: jeronimo.castrillon@tu-dresden.de katuscia.zedda@abinsula.com alfonso.rodriquezm@upm.es francesca.palumbo@unica.it
Short Description: Definition of an MLIR-based interoperability layer for the tools involved in MYRTUS Node-level Optimization and Deployment (step 3 of MYRTUS DPE), leveraging on existing dialects and contributing to them (e.g., for code mapping to the Multigrain CGRA Overlay).		
Baseline: The baseline consists of independent dialects in MLIR (e.g., for simple dataflow graphs, and ML operators) and existing tools (e.g., CGRA compiler tools chains) with no integration in MLIR. Some MLIR dialects are rather mature (e.g., linalg) and others less so. In the baseline there is no integrated solution and key dialects, and dialect extensions are missing to implement the planned functionality of the DPE.		TRL@M0: 2
MYRTUS Extension/Contribution: This is a new result, consistent on the seamless integration of node-level tools. The interoperability layer will enable a seamless programming and exploration flow, not possible today due to fragmented toolchains.		TRL@M36: 3-4
Plans and Expectation		
Assessment Plan@M18: Initial bilateral or tri-lateral interoperability between tools demonstrated in a small testbed. An example would be an external DSL integrated via MLIR into a mock application graph, with partially automatic code generation for a platform with RISC-V and a CGRA.		

¹⁷ The first iteration will consist in defining how the tools integrate and interoperate. The licensing will be defined at a later point, consistent with the licensing of the individual tools.

Expected Results@M18: Interoperability of 2-3 tools demonstrated.

4.3.2 Reachability of the Planned Operational Objective

At the time being, all the planned operational objectives (OO) are still considered reachable throughout the planned results. The tables below discuss in more details with respect to the Grant Agreement how the individual results are expected to contribute to the planned OOs. Please note that

- R19, R20, R21 and R23 have been linked to T3.OO.a “Provide a cross-layer modelling, analysis and simulation environment for the continuum leveraging standard languages to enable tools interoperability”, which was not the case in the Grant Agreement. They indeed contribute to carry out modelling, analysis and simulation at the edge node level. Therefore, they surely contribute to reach the planned OO.
- R20 has been linked to T3.OO.d “Provide support for virtualization, transparent programmability and management of the distributed heterogeneous cross-layer computing nodes, leveraging common entry points to facilitate specialised HW access and more flexible working points management” since Lingua Franca featuring the needed programming and compilation support surely contributes to reach the planned OO.
- R23 has been linked to T3.OO.e “Define design-time to runtime model-based strategies supporting MIRTO adaptivity mechanisms” since it represents the glue logic of node-level deployment support at the edge surely contributing to reach the planned OO.
- R17 mapping to OOs has been removed since SAM is going to be used within Pillar 2 only.

T3.OO.a - Provide a cross-layer modelling, analysis and simulation environment for the continuum leveraging standard languages to enable tools interoperability.

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R15	Modelio modules for TOSCA Designer and Attack Trees and Countermeasures design enable modelling of the entire cloud-fog-edge continuum, including threat modelling and associated countermeasures. The contributed Modelio module for TOSCA designer is an implementation of the OASIS TOSCA standard, thus providing out-of-the-box interoperability with other tools, both within MYRTUS as well as third-party ones complying with this standard
R16	DynAA is part of the MYRTUS DPE toolset and will enable simulation of system configurations for evaluation and optimization purposes. DynAA will be combined with the FREVO tool, providing simulation analysis for conducting evolutionary optimization. DynAA can simulate resources from different layers, allowing for analysis/estimation of KPIs in cross-layer deployments.
R18	FREVO will be probably interfaced with DynAA (or a comparable simulation framework) and will provide rules for the WL manager using evolutionary algorithms for the entire edge-fog-cloud continuum. This will be done using Modelio as an intermediate tool for the modelling part of the edge-fog-cloud continuum. Thus, we can reach an interoperability with other tools in the architecture supporting cross-layer deployment activities.
R19	Mocasin provides simulation and analysis support at the edge node level.
R20	Coordination languages such as Lingua Franca can be used to integrate components written in standard languages like C++ or Python. Therefore, it helps in addressing the interoperability aspects of the DPE.

R21	The CGRA-specific MLIR dialect included in the node-level compilation framework will enable the modelling of low-level architectural details, as well as the DSE of different code-to-overlay mapping approaches.
R23	Contributes at the edge node-level with an MLIR-based interoperability layer.

T3.OO.b - Provide advanced automatic code generation for secure WL definition, enabling automatic threat countermeasure synthesis and the generation of swarm agents (used by MIRTO for fog/edge orchestration).

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R15	Modelio modules provide out-of-the-box code generation facilities for Java as target language. The module and extensibility capabilities of Modelio make it possible to consider other target languages and platforms.
R18	The rules that present the behaviour of the agents come in different forms as an output of FREVO, such as, FSMs, ANNs or fuzzy rules. MYRTUS DPE will include the swarm orchestration rules in the automatic code generation of deployment configuration files and software component stubs.

T3.OO.c - Provide a node level optimization and deployment environment based on MLIR, to guarantee interoperability among MYRTUS tools and third-party ones.

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R19	Mocasin will be extended to receive application models from the MLIR-based compilation flow.
R20	Contributes new dialects and MLIR-based compilation flow for analysis, optimization and deployment.
R21	The Code-to-CGRA compilation framework will be based on MLIR to support common entry points with other toolchains that feature different device-specific optimizations in the back-end (i.e., binary generation at node level).
R22	The new release of MDC will contribute to offer node-level optimization and deployment over FPGA-based HMPSoC leveraging MLIR-to-hardware compilation flows.
R23	Contributes via the integration of results R19-R22 based on MLIR that can guarantee also third-party tools integration.

T3.OO.d - Provide support for virtualization, transparent programmability and management of the distributed heterogeneous cross-layer computing nodes, leveraging common entry points to facilitate specialised HW access and more flexible working points management.

<i>Mapped Result</i>	<i>Contribution</i>
R20	Contributes via programming models and compilation support.
R21	The Code-to-CGRA compilation framework will abstract all the low-level hardware details from the developer, accepting standard application descriptions (e.g., C or TensorFlow) and transparently (i.e., with no user intervention) generating application binaries for processor and CGRA.

R22	Contribution to transparent programmability and management through the automatic generation of APIs for configuring and using MDC accelerators
R23	Contributes with the integration of node-level design and programmability tools (R20-R22).

T3.OO.e - Define design-time to runtime model-based strategies supporting MIRTO adaptivity mechanisms.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R15	Modelio modelling modules can be extended with modelling concepts to support the MIRTO cognitive engine adaptivity mechanisms, and subsequent code generation capabilities. The models are expected to be enriched with the parameter data to be fed to the MIRTO cognitive engine.
R16	KPI Analysis results obtained from DynAA simulations can be kept in the knowledge base for use by optimizers and orchestration managers at runtime. In this case, DynAA system simulations (at design time) are provided as estimates supporting decisions during the runtime operation.
R19	Mocasin supports design-time exploration to create operating points for runtime adaptation and helps analyse potential runtime adaptation via simulation.
R20	The MLIR-based compilation flow can produce different variants, using different types of heterogeneous resources, that can be selected at runtime depending on context.
R21	The Code-to-CGRA compilation framework can provide alternative mappings for the same application to be exploited at runtime by MIRTO cognitive engine.
R22	MDC offers fast reconfiguration capabilities. Multiple working points (i.e. quantization level of a CNN) can be defined at design time and then selected at runtime by MIRTO cognitive engine.
R23	Contributes with the integration of edge node-level tools (R19-R22) for design, programming and deployment.

4.3.3 KPIs and M18 Assessment Plan

In the Grant Agreement we specified the KPIs to be achieved throughout Pillar 3 technologies, which are not changed. The tables below discuss how the identified results contribute to demonstrating those KPIs.

KPI3.1 - At least 2 MYRTUS tools and 2 external ones are made MLIR-interoperable.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R19-R23	R23 contributes with the integration of edge node-level tools (R19-R22) for design, programming and deployment that requires: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (R19) Mocasin to read-in application models generated from MLIR dialects. • (R20) Reactor model and adaptable dataflow captured in MLIR dialects. • (R20) Enablement of inserting external DSLs to represent computation within dataflow/reactor graph. The particular DSLs will depend on the

	<p>use cases, alternatives are ML DSL (like TensorFlow), image processing (like Halide), and/or tensor expressions (like CFDLang/TeiL).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (R21) The Code-to-CGRA compilation framework relies on MLIR at its core, providing at least a custom HW-level MLIR dialect to properly exploit parallelism mapping and deployment onto the target CGRA fabric. • MDC to be made MLIR-interoperable.
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KPI3.2 - Transparent support for at least 2 different HW-based computing devices using common entry points.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R19	Mocasin will be extended to model RISC-V execution and CGRAs.
R20	MLIR-based programming flow will support different heterogeneous internal/external backends: including Host execution, Edge devices (RISC-V + CGRA), extension to FPGA execution.
R21	Code-to-CGRA compilation targeting CGRA accelerators will accept common AI-oriented entry points (e.g., TensorFlow, ONNX).
R22	MDC will be made compatible with QONNX (and possibly corresponding MLIR dialect).
R23	Contributes via the integration of results R19-R22 based on MLIR that can guarantee also third-party tools integration.

KPI3.3 – Provide 10X productivity improvement using MYRTUS DPE to go from high-level specification down to deployment on specific nodes, with respect to the use of fragmented toolchains, patching tools with scripts and requiring subsequent user interventions.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R15	The use of high-level modelling based on standard modelling languages, and open standards such as OASIS TOSCA will ease communication between stakeholders, both technical and non-technical, automate development tasks such as code writing, streamline security analysis and resilience mechanisms development, thus contributing to achieve the productivity target of the MYRTUS DPE Toolchain in complementarity with the other tools.
R16	Simulation (at design time) of possible system configurations will provide estimates for performance, energy consumption, etc. in advance. During the runtime, such analysis will become indicative of the impact of orchestration decisions. This speeds up the decision-making process and produces better quality (informed) decisions which are less likely to need further interventions.
R18	The generated rules in FREVO, and the pre-engineered rules using nature-inspired swarm intelligence allow already during design time to classify a specific load in a specific (physical) environment. Rules refined at design-time by FREVO will then be used at run-time by the agents to ensure and effective system-wide optimization
R21	Transparent software-to-hardware translation mechanisms based on custom CGRA-oriented MLIR dialect(s) that can be easily integrated in a standard MLIR-based toolchain, taking advantage of already existing dialects, optimization passes and other back-/front-end components. This

	will not only improve productivity but also ease the adoption of customizable edge computing nodes.
R22	Tight and seamless integration of MDC with external HLS tool, i.e. with Vitis HLS through ONNX specification. This will facilitate the adoption of customizable edge nodes, in turn improving productivity.
R18, R19, R23	Supported by the enabled seamless interoperability of the tools (R19-R22) and the higher-level programming abstraction.

KPI3.4 - Provide at least: 1) 10-20% additional energy efficiency and processing/communication latency reduction, and 2) 10% quicker adaptation, with respect to those achievable by using MIRTO engine alone (KPI2.2), thanks to meta-information flow from design time to runtime.

Mapped Result	Contribution
R15	The Modelio modelling environment is easily extensible to include new meta-information at design time as required, which can immediately be operationalized in the information flow towards the runtime platforms, therefore contributing to the acceleration of the adaptation procedures.
R16	Simulation (at design time) of possible system configurations will provide estimates for performance, energy consumption, etc. in advance. During the runtime, such analysis will become indicative of the impact of orchestration decisions. This speeds up the decision-making process and produces better quality (informed) decisions which are less likely to need further interventions.
R18	Using the swarm intelligence approach at runtime can bring a quicker adaptation of the orchestration related to changing dynamic environment/inputs/etc. that will be evaluated.
R19	Mocasin enables Design Space Exploration to identify better mappings of applications to provide gains in energy-efficiency.
R20	The programming model (dataflow/reactors) enables optimizations and adaptations not easily possible with mainstream programming models. This makes it possible to produce different mappings at compile time. These mappings, in turn, reduce the exploration space at runtime ensuring quicker adaptation.
R21	Moving computation from software (embedded processor) to hardware (CGRA) is expected to contribute to point 1 (energy efficiency and computing performance improvement).
R22	Support for quantized NN and fixed-point arithmetic contributes to point 1 (energy efficiency improvement).

4.4 UC to technology Mapping

MYRTUS project results are expected to be assessed, in the long run, within the UC context. Therefore, we had an initial brainstorming session during the consortium meeting we had in Madrid in July to start the mapping process. We tried to implement a meet in the middle approach. On the one hand, UC providers highlighted their needs, on the other, technology providers¹⁸ tried to provide evidence on how their respective results might help in addressing those needs. The brainstorming was prepared in advance by distributing the Assessment Scenario tables that have been included in Section 3 to all the partners. Based on them the

¹⁸ All partners owning the Pillar 1, Pillar 2, and Pillar 3 results presented in this section

technology providers have started to consider, before the face-to-face meeting, the specific usage of their results into the UCs and, in presence, discussions on specific adoptions were held and consolidated into the tables that are included in the two subsections hereafter.

This mapping has to be considered extremely preliminary, the work in WP9 has just started (M7) and demonstration activities might affect it.

Currently, more than the 80% of results have already been mapped to MYRTUS Assessment Scenarios:

- Pillar 1 results are all mapped, as a demonstration of the need of the chosen assessment scenario for distributed continuum computing.
- R7 in Pillar 2 is expected to be developed in the second project iteration, so no plans for assessment have been established yet.
- R8 in Pillar 2 is expected to get closer to the UC in the second project period in terms of including UC-specific requirements for agent-based modelling and tests of the swarm library in simulation. Therefore, at the moment no mapping decisions have been taken yet.
- R9 and R12 in Pillar 2, according to the Grant Agreement, are planning a TRL around 3-4. Provided such a low target, it is still not feasible to plan their assessment within the project assessment scenario.
- Pillar 3 results are all mapped but will be demonstrated in an indirect manner. Indeed, design time tools will be used behind the scenes to carry out design space exploration, node customization, automatic code generation, and programming and to provide an initial optimal deployment over the MYRTUS infrastructure.

The final goal of the project is that most of the results are going to be assessed (directly or indirectly) within the context of the UCs. Nonetheless, that will depend a lot on the final achieved maturity and, in any case, for the M18 review we are expecting just partial integration of the demonstrators and lab assessment of the components. So, all plans below are perfectly inline with the Grant Agreement.

4.4.1 Mapping towards the Healthcare Assessment Scenario

Figure 4-8 drafts a preliminary minimal demonstrator for the Healthcare assessment scenario.

Figure 4-8 - Preliminary demonstrator for the Healthcare Assessment Scenario.

The patient's sensing and actuation system is composed of:

- **VR Headset with hand controllers:** it renders the scene to the user and tracks the hands position. It implements a bidirectional connection with the Embedded System (ES), which can be HTTP (by Wi-Fi) or Bluetooth (latency and bandwidth to be checked). The VR system integrates the data from the sensors connected to the ES and directly to the headset, using them locally to render the scene in Unity3D (tool for VR development¹⁹) and sending those relevant for the other players to the Game Server by Wi-Fi, receiving from it those related to the other players. VR controllers are connected to the headset via Bluetooth. *Selected Device:* Meta Quest 3
- **Haptic Joystick:** it acquires hand movement and provides strength feedback through its handle. It requires a bidirectional connection with the VR system, either directly or mediated by the ES (tunnelling), in both cases by a USB connection. Motors in the device turn on and are updated approximately 1000 times a second. *Selected Device:* Novint Falcon Robot
- **EMG sensors:** The EMG sensing platform acquires the electromyography signal from the smart garment. Every node includes the analog front-end, the ADC and a wireless connection to a receiving unit. The data streaming is unidirectional (from the sensors), provided theatre common handshake and config commands are issued by the receiving unit. The connection is wireless. Different off-the-shelf devices are currently under evaluation. One option is OTB Due. Every sensing node can acquire a pair of muscles (2 signals). Data is sent in raw format, sampled at 2048 Hz, via Bluetooth 4.0 to Windows/Android either directly (Android) or by a USB dongle (Windows). As OTB Due became a legacy product, OTB DUE+ can be adopted, which presents similar features but connection through a TCP socket over Wi-Fi, with sampling @2kHz. Linux implementation is not reported and will be investigated with the manufacturers. Similarly, other sensing platforms can be used, like those provided by COMETA (Pico EMG) or BTS (FREEEMG). Raw data needs to be processed (envelope extraction) in real-time for use. Typical processing includes bandpass IIR filtering, rectification, smoothing by a low-pass filter, downsampling (down to 50-100 Hz). This processing can be performed either in Unity3D or on the ES. If multiple sensors, ES is preferable.
- **Vibrotactile actuator:** it gives vibrotactile feedback to the player. It requires a unidirectional wireless (Bluetooth classic or low energy) connection from ES. Communication requires a very limited bandwidth. Different devices are currently under evaluation:
 - *Option 1:* Commercial nodes like MetaMotionRL + <https://mbientlab.com/store/metamotionrl-p/>
 - *Option 2:* custom module with the simplest BT connection.

In the assessment scenarios, at least four different computing platforms are envisioned:

- **Multiplayer Server:** it normally belongs to the cloud, but it can be hosted also in a fog device if needed. It runs the game server. It MUST be able to run an executable file (Windows, Mac or Linux).
- **Backend Server:** It handles Player's data, Therapist's data and Therapist Control Panel. It runs on the Cloud or on the Fog and it must be able to support .net / .net core and postgresSQL.
- **Headset:** it belongs to the edge. It runs the client for the player and renders the VR scene, using the information from the local sensors and from the sensors and actions of the other players (multiplayer application). It MUST be able to run Unity3D, but it cannot be seen as a

¹⁹ <https://unity.com/>

resource capable of exchanging workloads with the continuum since, being a closed device, it will not host any MIRTO cognitive engine agent.

- **Edge ES:** it belongs to the edge. It collects data from sensors and drives actuators for a single local player. It will play the role of hub for wearable sensing and actuation. Provides tunnelling features (sensors to headset and back) and processing capabilities to relieve the headset from real-time signal processing.
- **MYRTUS Infrastructure Component [TBD]:** an edge or fog platform to run the VAs, which are the specific WLS that MIRTO cognitive engine will orchestrate. It **MUST** be able to run a Unity3D executable file. Ideally, in the long term, it **MIGHT** be the ES itself (there might be limitations related to the capability of the Linux-based OS on FPGA-based edge devices), but as a first attempt, we could use a fog desktop device.

From a high-level perspective, it is expected to use MYRTUS technical pillars as follows.

- Pillar 1 - The demonstrator infrastructure is compliant with the onion-like MYRTUS reference infrastructure, and it is expected to adopt components of Pillar 1.
- Pillar 2 - Edge/Fog/Cloud components capable of running the VAs will run MIRTO cognitive engine agents that will transparently handle the workload movement.
- Pillar 3 - MYRTUS DPE will be used to support modelling and deployment.

Regarding the partners'/technologies' involvement in these scenario, beside UNICA-MeDSP lab (UC owner) and REPLY (responsible for the game server side, VR game logic and design, Backend Server + Frontend UI), which were involved in the definition since the beginning, Table 4-3 summarises the ongoing discussions on MYRTUS technology mapping with respect to this assessment scenario.

Table 4-3 - MYRTUS technology mapping with respect to the Healthcare UC.

Result	Owner	Potential Mapping
R1	UNICA UNISS	Usage of both R1 and R2 as possible ES where to offload and execute the signal processing algorithms (should be already there to be taken as inputs "as is") that process the physiological signals coming from the patient (can also come from a dataset if GDPR issues arise).
R2	UPM	The feasibility of running the Unity3D engine at the edge is currently under evaluation.
R3	ABI	The Multi-Sensor Gateway is placed at the fog level. It could support the system adaptivity in relation to the management of VAs according to the number of patients available (or other needs). The feasibility of running the Unity3D engine (supported by a Linux distribution or by a hybrid Linux-Android one) in the gateway is currently under analysis.
R4	HIRO	Discussion on possible HIRO involvement in this Assessment Scenario are still ongoing, but the FMDC will be able to deploy the executable game server (as a containerized application) provided by REPLY and has the capacity to handle VAs execution and management.
R6	UNISS UNICA UPM	It is still unclear whether the MIRTO cognitive engine will be used or not at the edge to manage VAs, since the Unity3D engine at the edge is

R11	UNISS UNICA UPM ABI	currently under evaluation. Nonetheless, edge devices will anyhow integrate MIRTO-compliant cognitive engine agents to manage WL offloading and working points selection.
R13	USI	These technologies are meant to be transversal and fully applicable at the UC level. Since security is potentially extremely important in healthcare scenarios, at least two levels of security and two different implements of the same level of security will be modelled for the components involved in this scenario. MIRTO will be capable of using those models.
R14	ARK	Enabling the continuum within the scenario cloud-edge infrastructure to schedule/move the VAs based on the MIRTO cognitive engine decisions.
R15	SOFT, USI	Modelling of the Healthcare scenario application architecture with TOSCA (VR devices, body sensors...), provide attack-defence trees, and UML models (application structure and behaviour). For specifying deployment processes, we can use: 1) For high level modelling using natural language: BPMN 2) For precise modelling: UML state machine or UML Activity diagrams (we can use the UML Event construct to represent time intervals, constraints, ...).
R18	LAKE	Perform agent-based modelling of the use case and map the UC agents (sensors as MIRTO edge agents and fog devices as MIRTO fog agents) to the swarm-based orchestration concept.
R19	TUD	In the context of the application scenario, Mocasin will be used to estimate and explore the mappings for different configurations of the target platform.
R20	TUD	Key operations and algorithms that require acceleration will be modelled with DSLs/MLIR dialects and connected with the new MLIR dialects for adaptive execution.
R21	UPM	The MLIR-based Code-to-CGRA compilation toolchain can be used to automatically compile and map the signal processing algorithms into the heterogeneous RISC-V (SW) + CGRA (HW) edge nodes. Ideal entry point for the algorithms would be C-based descriptions.
R22	UNISS, UNICA	Signal processing accelerators to be included in the ES will be based on new features of MDC.
R23	TUD, ABI, UPM, UNICA	Compiler receives representations of key kernels (e.g., at the linear algebra level), high level graph of how the kernels are interconnected, and operating modes, and will derive optimised implementations. Node-level tools of MYRTUS DPE will produce optimised implementations. This is embedded in the larger application modelled in Modelio. This means that the compiler does not optimise the entire application but focuses on key parts extracted in Step 2 of the DPE.

4.4.2 Mapping towards the Smart Mobility Scenario [TNO-CRF]

Figure 4-9 shows the envisioned location for the traffic intersection safety demonstrator for the Smart Mobility Scenario. Two adjacent intersections in the city of Helmond will be equipped with 5 camera systems to monitor all traffic users, detect potential conflicts between road users such as potential collisions and jaywalking, and warn cooperative vehicle systems. The intersections are on the ring road around the city centre. The city centre is on the southside in this figure. The ring road is very busy with vehicles driving around the city centre or entering and exiting the ring road to parking areas, the marketplace and shops. Heavy goods vehicles are also diverted over this ring road. To the North of the ring road there are schools, education centres and residential areas. Large volumes of pedestrians and bicyclists cross the intersections. For example, large groups of students cross the intersections via the two roads to the South to railway and bus stations and the schools to the North.

Figure 4-9 - Preliminary demonstrator for the Smart Mobility Assessment Scenario.

The intersection safety monitoring and warning system is composed of:

- **Camera system:** 5 camera systems will be installed on poles to detect and track all types of road users across the intersections. The coloured areas show the field of view of the cameras. Four cameras fully cover the intersection to the East where most pedestrians and cyclists cross. One camera covers the intersection to the West and the connecting road between the intersections to detect and track the pedestrians and cyclists that cross the ring road somewhere between the intersections.
- **Cooperative traffic light controller:** both intersections are controlled with traffic lights. The traffic light controller (TLC) adapts the status of the lights for vehicles, pedestrians and cyclists separately and in function of detected traffic. The TLC are also cooperative and use short-and long-range communication to cooperative and connected vehicles, e.g. to exchange traffic light status and timing information, and to detect approaching vehicles over longer distances. The TLC is not directly connected to the camera system in this project.
- **Road users:** normal road users participating in daily traffic, such as passenger and heavy goods vehicles, buses, bicyclists and pedestrians.
- **Connected and cooperative vehicles:** Connected vehicles are private vehicles that are connected to traffic information and traffic safety services. These services provide information on traffic light status, speed advice and hazard warnings to drivers, and collect floating car data. Cooperative vehicles are private and public vehicles with on-board equipment for V2X short- or long-range communication. The messages to the connected and cooperative vehicles are exchanged via the Cooperative Intelligent Transport System (C-

ITS) Broker in this project. Occasionally also cooperative emergency vehicles are passing that can request priority at the traffic lights.

The following computing platforms are envisioned:

- **Camera:** edge device running image processing software for the detection and tracking of all road users, fusion with data from connected and cooperative vehicles and detection of potential conflicts between road users.
- **Fog server:** a separate server will be installed in the cabinet at the intersection. The fog server will be used to support and orchestrate the image processing, detection, tracking and fusion of the individual camera systems locally and to the cloud. This server also connects to the C-ITS broker for the exchange of C-ITS messages from the TLC, connected and cooperative vehicles.
- **Cloud server:** a cloud server will be used for similar purposes as the fog server to support and orchestrate the image processing, detection, tracking and fusion of the individual camera systems locally on the cameras and the fog server. Like the fog server, the cloud server can also connect to the C-ITS Broker for C-ITS messages.
- **C-ITS Broker:** a broker in the cloud that publishes and subscribes to national access points to exchange C-ITS messages with the traffic light controller, connected and cooperative vehicles. The CITS Broker exchanges the CITS messages with the camera systems, fog server and cloud server. The CITS broker also encodes and decodes the C-ITS messages in a format suitable for the camera, fog and cloud server. This server may also be used to connect to services for tracking road users, conflict detection and the generation of warning messages to connected and cooperative vehicles.

From a high-level perspective, it is expected to use MYRTUS technical pillars as follows.

- Pillar 1 - The demonstrator infrastructure is compliant with the onion-like MYRTUS reference infrastructure, and it is expected to adopt components of Pillar 1.
- Pillar 2 - Edge/Fog/Cloud components for the detection, tracking and conflict detection will run MIRTO cognitive engine agents that will transparently handle the workload movement.
- Pillar 3 - MYRTUS DPE will be used to support modelling and deployment.

TNO and CRF provide the intersection safety monitoring and warning system and servers for the Mobility Use Case. Table 4-4 summarises the ongoing discussions on MYRTUS technology mapping with respect to this assessment scenario.

Table 4-4 - MYRTUS technology mapping with respect to the Smart Mobility UC.

Result	Owner	Potential Mapping
R1	UNISS UNICA	[Actual HW deployment of R1 and R2 edge nodes in the Traffic UC is not expected, but we think an alternative synthetic scenario can be evaluated] Proof of the AI at the edge capabilities within the context of the CRF algorithms is planned for both R1 and R2, they can be both potentially used as one of the edge computing platforms where to offload and execute the AI-based image processing algorithms (should be already there, preferably as TF/ONNX models, to be taken as inputs "as is") that process the images coming from smart cameras (e.g., Canon) or plain COTS ones directly connected to the edge (can also come from a dataset if GDPR issues arise).
R2	UPM	
R4	HIRO	The usage of R4 in this context involves different ongoing discussions. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Deployment of RMU unit on FMDC is still under evaluation

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Storage of metadata information of detection results is still to be defined, for example detection bounding box, classification (i.e. human, car, truck), confidence level, etc. Detection processing algorithms can be executed on FMDC, but there is a risk of GDPR compliance: Real video can not be sent to FMDC, only processed metadata to be checked.
R5	TNO	At least 2 cloud providers, where parts of the application can be mapped, will be emulated. These cloud providers emulated environments will have Gaia-X trust models. In the demonstration activities, the goal is to show how these models are checked (authenticated) before allowing a deployment. We can also emulate cases where a provider does not have a compliant trust model, to show that deployment is not possible in these cases.
R10, R16, R17	TNO	MIRTO agents -- and the MIRTO managers within them -- will be able to create dynamic service composition for the system deployment depending on actual resource usage and KPI goals. At this phase, the dynamic allocation is still limited to within the resource pool of an agent. DynAA (R16) and SAM (17) will be combined in the MIRTO agent to realise the dynamic service composition at runtime.
R13	USI	These technologies are meant to be transversal and fully applicable at the UC level. Since security is potentially extremely important in Smart Mobility scenarios, at least two levels of security and two different implements of the same level of security will be modelled for the components involved in this scenario. MIRTO will be capable of using those models.
R14	ARK	Enabling the continuum within the scenario cloud-edge infrastructure to schedule/move the workloads based on the MIRTO cognitive engine decisions.
R15	SOFT, USI	Modelling of the traffic application architecture with TOSCA (camera devices, CCAM vehicles), attack-defence trees, and UML models (application structure and behaviour). For specifying deployment processes, the current idea is to use: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1) For high level modelling using natural language: BPMN 2) For precise modelling: UML state machine or UML Activity diagrams (we can use the UML Event construct to represent time intervals, constraints, ...)
R18	LAKE HIRO	Perform agent-based modelling of the use case and map the UC agents (cars/cameras/other infrastructure as MIRTO edge agents and fog devices as MIRTO fog agents) to the swarm-based orchestration concept. Use the data from the use case to perform swarm resource allocation on use-case-specific data resource demand (including limitations like time sensitivity, privacy, etc.) on use-case-specific resources (MIRTO edge and fog agents) (e.g., cars, cameras, fog nodes). We still need to clarify whether parts of the final demo can be physical, others can be used in a virtual way

		(this would guarantee the complexity behind the many agents where a global behaviour in the form of a swarm-based resource allocation emerges).
R19	TUD	Mocasin will be used to estimate and explore the possible configurations to meet the requirements of the applications in the different modes.
R20	TUD	In the MLIR modelling required for R20, the new dialects for adaptive execution will be used.
R21	UPM	<i>[Actual HW deployment of a RISC-V+CGRA node in the Traffic UC is not expected, but we think an alternative synthetic scenario can be evaluated]</i> The MLIR-based Code-to-CGRA compilation toolchain can be used to automatically compile and map the AI-based image processing algorithms into the heterogeneous RISC-V (SW) + CGRA (HW) edge nodes. Mandatory entry points for the algorithms would be TF/ONNX-based descriptions.
R22	UNISS, UNICA	<i>[Actual HW deployment of HMPSoC accelerators in the Traffic UC is not expected, but we think an alternative synthetic scenario can be evaluated]</i> Edge processing accelerators (see R1) compatible with the adoption in smart cameras for this scenario will be based on new features of MDC. We expect here to assess the new ONNX to hardware features of MDC.
R23	TUD, ABI, UPM, UNICA	<i>[Actual edge processing on FPGA-based nodes in the Traffic UC is not expected, but we think an alternative synthetic scenario can be evaluated]</i> Compiler receives ONNX representations of the different models, operational modes (easy, hard), pipeline of processing, and requirements/estimations. Compiler precomputes static mappings (at design time) to the nodes for the different modes.

- **Technical Assumption(s) or Customer Need(s):** This column should reference the source of the requirement (Grant agreement, technical assumption, UC needs).
- **Requirement:** Description of the functional/technical requirement.
- **Classification:** This column should be populated with the classification of the requirement (Functional, Technical, Interface, Performance, Other).
 - *Functional:* define the expected functions or capabilities of the system or its components.
 - *Technical:* define technical aspects and issues to be addressed, for the system or its components to execute successfully.
 - *Interface:* define the interfaces for the system to interact with another system, or for a component to interact with another component.
 - *Other:* If a requirement is not Functional, Technical, Interface, it's defined as Other, and an explanation is reported in the "Additional Comments" column.
- **Status:** This column should be populated with the current status of the requirement (Draft, Proposed, Reviewed, Agreed, Rejected).
 - *Draft:* The Requirement has been defined but it's not ready to be reviewed.
 - *Proposed:* The Requirement has been defined and it's ready to be reviewed.
 - *Reviewed:* The Requirement has been Reviewed.
 - *Agreed:* The Requirement has been Accepted.
 - *Rejected:* The Requirement has been Rejected. A comment in the "Additional Comments" column is required, to remind the reasons for rejection.
- **MYRTUS Pillar:** This column should reference the MYRTUS Pillar it applies to.
 - *Pillar 1:* MYRTUS reference infrastructure
 - *Pillar 2:* MIRTO cognitive engine
 - *Pillar 3:* MYRTUS DPE
- **Additional Comments:** Use this column to detail the Classification, if the requirement is classified as "Other", and for any additional comment.

5.1.2 MYRTUS Requirement Checklist

The *MYRTUS Requirements Checklist* is the tool used to analyse the set of requirements against a set of criteria defined in the checklist. Table 5-1 depicts the criteria checklist. For each criterion, it is defined a *Checklist ID*, a description (*General Review Criteria*), the *Comment/Status* and a *Score*, which is assigned as follows:

- **green**, if all the requirements meet the criteria, or all the findings have been solved.
- **yellow**, if there are one or more requirements that do not meet the criteria, but appropriate mitigations are in place.
- **red**, if there are one or more requirements that do not meet the criteria, and appropriate mitigations are not in place.

Once the set of requirements is checked against all the criteria, any relevant comment is reported in the Additional Comments box (Table 5-2), and the final decision is reported in the Final Decision box (Table 5-3).

Table 5-1 - Requirement Review Checklist

Requirement Review Checklist			
Check-list ID	General Review Criteria	Comment/Status	Score
1	Is the requirements template in accordance with the defined and selected methods for the project?		

2	The specific terminology (acronyms, parameter names) is known explained or referred			
3	Are the requirements consistent? Is the same word being always used for the same concept consistently?			
4	Are all the required functions and capabilities specified according to the Classification list?			
5	Are the requirements atomic (singular respectively non-redundant)?			
6	Are the requirements understandable?			
7	Are the requirements unambiguous?			
8	Are the requirements concise?			
9	Are the requirements uniquely identified and complete?			
10	Are all the requirements referred to the MYRTUS Pillars?			
11	Have all the specified requirements been analysed, including their interdependencies to ensure correctness, technical feasibility, and to support risk identification?			
12	Are the requirements feasible?			
13	Are the requirements necessary?			
14	Are the requirements analysed regarding the impact on the operating environment?			
15	Are the requirements and their updates to requirements baselined and communicated to all affected parties?			

Table 5-2 - Requirement Review Checklist - comments box.

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS

Table 5-3 - Requirement Review Checklist - final decision box.

FINAL DECISION

5.2 Phase 1 - Requirements proposal

MYRTUS requirements are defined to address all the MYRTUS technical operations objectives (T.OO) defined in the Grant Agreement, security needs and technical discussions about the components, and the UCs needs. For the sake of discussion, we divide hereafter the MYRTUS requirements into three groups (Generic requirements, Specific requirements, UC-related requirements) that are described in the following subsections.

Please, note that so far 54 project requirements have been proposed, but technical discussions are still ongoing (in the context for WPs related to the MYRTUS Pillars) to define more detailed requirements necessary for implementation. The updated and refined set of requirements will be reported, as planned, in Deliverable D2.1 at M22.

5.2.1 Generic requirements

This set of requirements is meant to drive Pillar1, Pillar 2 and Pillar 3 development, respectively, in WP3-4, WP5-6, and WP7-8. It is directly derived from the T.OOs that have been made atomic and clarified to follow the requirements template defined in the MYRTUS Requirements Traceability Matrix.

For instance, the MYRTUS requirement 001 has been derived from the MYRTUS T1.OO.a “Provide a layered reference infrastructure representing the skeleton of MYRTUS compliant systems, capable of ubiquitous data acquisition and distributed intelligent decision-making” as follows:

Example of generic requirement related to MYRTUS T1.OO.a	
ID	001
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	T1.OO.a (Grant Agreement)

Requirement	The MYRTUS reference infrastructure SHOULD be capable of ubiquitous data acquisition and distributed intelligent decision-making.
Classification	Functional
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure
Additional Comments	---

Another example is given by MYRTUS T2.OO.a “*Formalization of a generic multi-layer cognitive self-adaptation engine constituted of different resource- and layer-specific agents, implementing customised management*” from which, two requirements (004 and 005) have been derived as follows:

Example of generic requirement related to MYRTUS T2.OO.a	
ID	004
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	T2.OO.a (Grant Agreement)
Requirement	The MYRTUS cognitive engine SHOULD be formalised as a generic multi-layer cognitive self-adaptation engine.
Classification	Other (see additional comments)
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	This requirement is related to the scientific achievement of defining a generic novel orchestration scheme for self adaptive computing continuum systems.

Example of generic requirement related to MYRTUS T2.OO.a	
ID	005
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	T2.OO.a (Grant Agreement)
Requirement	The MYRTUS cognitive engine SHOULD be constituted of different resource- and layer- specific agents for customised management.

Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	---

5.2.2 Specific requirements

This set of requirements refines the generic requirements and is derived by technical- and security-related discussions keeping into account also the alignment with the EU-CEI documentations and guidelines. This first set of requirements is necessary to define the MYRTUS infrastructure and enable the computing continuum; it is meant to identify a preliminary set of technologies, models, standards, etc., to which the implementation activities should be aligned.

For instance, starting from requirement 001, described in the previous section, it was clear the need to enable data sharing. Discussions about it led to identifying the need for a Distributed Knowledge Base (DKB) to make data available to other layers for analysis and decision making (requirement 022). This further led to discussions related to the interface to be adopted (requirements 026) and to data synchronisation (requirement 030).

Example of specific requirements related to Pillar 1	
ID	022
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Technical Discussions
Requirement	A distributed knowledge base SHOULD be implemented to enable data sharing between MYRTUS components in different layers
Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure
Additional Comments	TO DEFINE: Interfaces to DKB and what data SHOULD be stored in DKB. E.g. CockroachDB, ETCD, Apache Cassandra

Example of specific requirement related to both Pillar 1 and Pillar 2	
ID	026

Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Technical Discussions
Requirement	MIRTO agents SHOULD define and expose an interface (request) to the knowledge base component. Knowledge base components should implement this interface.
Classification	Interface
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	TO DEFINE: An interface specification to be used by the MIRTO agent when retrieving resources configuration and resource status. Providers of resource information, such as resource registries, resource monitors, etc. should implement this interface.

Example of specific requirements related to both Pillar 1 and Pillar 2	
ID	030
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Technical Discussions
Requirement	The distributed knowledge base SHOULD be able to synchronize data between different layers and/or databases at a configured rate.
Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	The idea is that the KB has mechanisms to synch data between the layers without the need of any external agent.

Above examples are mainly derived from discussions related to Pillar 1 and Pillar 2 that are two sides of the same coin. Indeed, being related respectively to the MYRTUS infrastructure and to the MIRTO cognitive engine, they are necessary to implement the computing continuum.

Other technical discussions also led to the proposal of requirements related to the MYRTUS DPE. For instance, requirement 019 derived from T3.OOe is further refined by requirements 032 and 033. These three requirements are reported in the following table:

Example of specific requirements related to Pillar 3	
ID	019
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	T3.OO.e (Grant Agreement)
Requirement	The MYRTUS DPE SHOULD make available design-time to runtime model-based strategies supporting MIRTO adaptivity mechanisms.
Classification	Functional
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 3 - MYRTUS DPE
Additional Comments	Refined in requirements 31 and 32

Example of specific requirements related to Pillar 3	
ID	032
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Technical Discussions
Requirement	MYRTUS DPE SHOULD export exporting different implementations of a given application (or application component) alongside meta-information about its resource requirements (number of cores, CGRA usage, ...) and expected execution metrics (e.g., latency, throughout, and energy consumption).
Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 3 - MYRTUS DPE
Additional Comments	---

Example of specific requirements related to Pillar 3	
ID	033
Technical Assumption(s)	Technical Discussions

and/or Customer Need(s)	
Requirement	MYRTUS DPE SHOULD expose trade-offs to be used at runtime to select a fitting implementation based on availability of resources and application requirements (similar to node-level auto-tuning approaches).
Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 3 - MYRTUS DPE
Additional Comments	---

One of the aspects to keep into account in systems such as the ones considered in MYRTUS, is the need for security. This requires that all the components provide security primitives such as encryption, hashing, and key encapsulation mechanisms. A discussion on this topic led to the definition of a set of requirements, two of which are reported hereinafter as examples.

Example of security requirement	
ID	034
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Technical Discussions on Security
Requirement	MYRTUS components SHOULD support at least two security levels.
Classification	Functional
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	This requirement allows the security manager to adapt to other non-functional requirements

Example of security requirement	
ID	035
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Technical Discussions on Security
Requirement	MYRTUS components SHOULD provide at least two

	implementations for each supported security level.
Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	

5.2.3 UC-related requirements

MYRTUS is not a UC-driven project, and UCs are meant to be the assessment ground for MYRTUS technologies. Nevertheless, the definition of a set of application specific requirements is necessary for the implementation of the UCs themselves.

Some UC-related needs are general functional or technical needs, that can be generalised to define requirements necessary for the implementation of MYRTUS technologies. An example is given by the following:

Example of UC-related generic requirement	
ID	042
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Use Cases
Requirement	MIRTO cognitive engine SHOULD provide adaptivity at runtime to the variation of number of components in the system.
Classification	Functional
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	Pillar 1 - MYRTUS reference infrastructure Pillar 2 - MIRTO cognitive engine
Additional Comments	---

Other requirements are specific for the implementation of the UCs and cannot be generalised. For instance:

Example of UC-related specific requirement - Health UC	
ID	049
Technical Assumption(s)	Healthcare Use Case

and/or Customer Need(s)	
Requirement	Hub devices to be used at the edge SHOULD provide specific connectivity supports: Wi-Fi and Bluetooth for the VR headset, Bluetooth and USB for other sensors.
Classification	Technical
Status	Proposed
MYRTUS Pillar	---
Additional Comments	This requirement is not related to the development of MYRTUS, but to its assessment. Therefore, it is not related to any specific Pillar.

Example of UC-related specific requirement - Mobility UC	
ID	054
Technical Assumption(s) and/or Customer Need(s)	Mobility Use Case
Requirement	The Edge/Fog/Cloud devices should be capable to receive, decode and analyse videos to detect road users with at least 10 frames per second
Classification	Performance
Status	Draft
MYRTUS Pillar	---
Additional Comments	This requirement is not related to the development of MYRTUS, but to its assessment. Therefore, it is not related to any specific Pillar.

5.3 Phase 2 - Requirements Acceptance

Each requirement has passed through iterations among partners that agreed on them, and most of the requirements are currently in the Proposed status.

To be formally accepted and pass through the Agreed status, the requirements set need to be checked against the Criteria defined in the *MYRTUS Requirements Checklist*. The check, review and acceptance of requirements is managed by the coordination team; in case of requirements that do not meet the criteria, further iterations with the WP leaders are meant to be carried out.

It is not yet possible to go through the process for the requirements acceptance, since more technical discussions, carried out in the technical WPs, are necessary complete the set of requirements and to evaluate their technical feasibility and check them against Criteria 11-14, however a first iteration to check all the requirements against the other Criteria has been done. The result is reported in the following tables. Please note that, as planned, the whole process will be finalised in WP2 during the second iteration of the project and reported in Deliverable D2.1 at M22.

Table 5-4 - Requirement Review Checklist [Status @ M8].

Requirement Review Checklist					
Check-list ID	General Review Criteria	Comment/Status	Score		
1	Is the requirements template in accordance with the defined and selected methods for the project?		X		
2	The specific terminology (acronyms, parameter names) is known, explained or referred		X		
3	Are the requirements consistent? Is the same word being always used for the same concept consistently?		X		
4	Are all the required functions and capabilities specified according to the Classification list?		X		
5	Are the requirements atomic (singular respectively non-redundant)?		X		
6	Are the requirements understandable?		X		
7	Are the requirements unambiguous?		X		
8	Are the requirements concise?		X		
9	Are the requirements uniquely identified and complete?		X		
10	Are all the requirements referred to the MYRTUS Pillars?	<i>Exceptions in the case of use-case specific requirements, for which this doesn't apply.</i>	X		
11	Have all the specified requirements been analysed, including their interdependencies to ensure correctness, technical	<i>Need the complete list of requirements for checking the whole set against all the criteria.</i>			

	feasibility, and to support risk identification?				
12	Are the requirements feasible?	<i>Need the complete list of requirements for checking the whole set against all the criteria.</i>			
13	Are the requirements necessary?	<i>Need the complete list of requirements for checking the whole set against all the criteria.</i>			
14	Are the requirements analysed regarding the impact on the operating environment?	<i>Need the complete list of requirements for checking the whole set against all the criteria.</i>			
15	Are the requirements and their updates to requirements baselined and communicated to all affected parties?		X		

Table 5-5 - Requirement Review Checklist - comments box [Status @ M8].

ADDITIONAL COMMENTS
<i>Need the complete list of requirements for checking the whole set against all the criteria.</i>

Table 5-6 - Requirement Review Checklist - final decision box [Status @ M8].

FINAL DECISION
<i>Pending.</i>

6 Conclusions

D1.1 reported on T1.1 and T1.2 activities, focussing on

- detailing the assessment scenarios, their characteristics, needs, and initial requirements (Section 3);
- refining the main technical pillar ideas, with emphasis on the internal architecture of each pillar and providing baseline and expectations of all the results per pillar, which have also been mapped on the assessment scenarios (Section 4);
- technical KPIs per pillar (Section 4.1.3, Section 4.2.3, and Section 4.3.3);
- the process to gather the project-level technical requirements (Section 5).

As soon as the development of the technical activities continues at the WP level, we expect to be able to refine the interface among the technical pillars, the UC to technology mapping (despite 80% of results have already been mapped towards the Assessment Scenarios), and the technical requirements.

We consider this document a live document, and a formal update will be provided at M22 by “D2.1 UC - Needs, requirements and KPIs v2” considering the feedback from partial technology assessment (WP9 outcome), M18 review, and synergy-related activities (with the other computing continuum initiatives/projects and the cluster 3 projects).

7 References

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8 Appendix 1 - Healthcare scenario pictures

Section 3 pictures: Application (Figure 8-1) and Deployment (Figure 8-2) diagrams.

Figure 8-1 - Healthcare Scenario Application Diagram.

Figure 8-2 - Healthcare Scenario Deployment Diagram.

9 Appendix 2 - Section 2 Smart Mobility scenario pictures
 Section 3 pictures: Application (Figure 9-1) and Deployment (Figure 9-2) diagrams.

Figure 9-1 – Smart Mobility Scenario Application Diagram.

Figure 9-2 – Smart Mobility Scenario Deployment Diagram.